

Catálogo de Métricas

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Tabela 1: Metrics Catalog: Block Propagation

Metric	Block Propagation
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for a newly created block to spread across the blockchain network, measured from the moment it is created by a node until a significant fraction of the other nodes (e.g., 50% or 90%) receive and accept it.
Objective	To evaluate the speed and efficiency of communication among network nodes, since delays in block propagation can lead to invalid blocks, chain conflicts, and reduced system security.
Equation	Propagation _{p%} = time until p% of the nodes receive the block – block announcement time. A complementary measure is $\rho_{p\%} = \frac{\text{Propagation}_{p\%}}{\text{Block Interval}}$.
Comment	The lower the propagation time, the better the network performance. High values indicate a higher risk of block conflicts and lower security. It is recommended to observe high percentiles (such as p90 or p95), as they reflect network behavior under more critical conditions.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	1) Select the percentage of nodes to be considered (e.g., 50% or 90%). 2) Record the time when the block is created and announced to the network. 3) Measure the time at which each node receives the block. 4) Compute the time required for the chosen percentage of nodes to receive the block. 5) Analyze mean values and percentiles to compare different network conditions.

References	1) Blockchain Layer Zero: Characterizing the Bitcoin Network through Measurements, Models, and Simulations 2) A Novel Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Model for IIoMT
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Tabela 2: Metrics Catalog: Block Size

Metric	Block Size
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of data that composes a block in a blockchain, including the header, transactions, and additional control information.
Objective	To evaluate the use of blockchain network resources, since larger blocks allow more transactions to be included but may increase validation time, propagation delay, and the risk of congestion.
Equation	$S_b = S_{header} + \sum \text{transaction sizes} + \text{metadata}$. For multi-block analysis, the average block size over a given time window can be used.
Comment	Larger blocks increase the processing capacity of the network but tend to raise validation and propagation times, especially in congested networks. Block size should be tuned together with other parameters, such as block interval and transaction selection policies.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain and the analysis period. 2) Collect the size of each block from nodes or blockchain explorers. 3) Compute statistics such as the mean, median, and percentiles of block sizes. 4) Relate block size to delay metrics, such as validation and propagation time. 5) Compare different network configurations or consensus parameters.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Blockchain Layer Zero: Characterizing the Bitcoin Network through Measurements, Models, and Simulations 2) Effect of Miner Incentive on the Confirmation Time of Bitcoin Transactions 3) HealthBlock: A Secure Blockchain-Based Healthcare Data Management System

Tabela 3: Metrics Catalog: Block Time

Metric	Block Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time interval between the creation of two consecutive blocks in a blockchain. This time indicates how frequently new blocks are added to the chain.
Objective	To evaluate how quickly the blockchain produces new blocks, directly influencing transaction latency, processing capacity, and the experience of applications that depend on the network.
Equation	$BT_i = T_i - T_{i-1}$. The average block time can be computed as the mean or median of the intervals between consecutive blocks over a given period.
Comment	Shorter block times make the network more responsive, allowing transactions to be included more frequently. However, very short block times may affect the stability and security of consensus. It is recommended to also analyze high percentiles (p90, p95) to identify variability and spikes.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain, the consensus type, and the observation period. 2) Collect timestamps of consecutive blocks using nodes or APIs. 3) Compute the time interval between successive blocks. 4) Obtain statistics such as mean, median, and percentiles. 5) Relate the results to metrics such as transaction latency and throughput.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Blockchain for IoT: A Consensus Mechanism Analysis 2) A Blockchain-based Trust Management Framework with Verifiable Interactions 3) SDBGPChain 4) Smart Microgrid Energy Market 5) Towards a Smarter IoT Environment with EVM-enabling Ledgers

Tabela 4: Metrics Catalog: Delay

Metric	Delay
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for information to travel from the sending point to the receiving point in a blockchain or distributed system, such as a transaction, a block, or a message exchanged between nodes.
Objective	To evaluate the speed of communication in the network, since high delays affect transaction confirmation, increase chain conflicts, and degrade time-sensitive applications such as IoT and V2X.
Equation	Delay = reception time – sending time. Depending on the context, it may represent block propagation delay, transaction delay, or end-to-end application delay.
Comment	The lower the delay, the better the system performance. High values indicate a higher risk of conflicts, lower network stability, and poorer experience for real-time applications. It is recommended to observe high percentiles (p95 or p99), which reflect critical situations under load or mobility.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clearly define the sending event and the receiving event. 2) Collect sending and receiving times on nodes with synchronized clocks. 3) Perform measurements under different network conditions, loads, and topologies. 4) Compute the delay distribution (median, p90, p95, p99). 5) Relate delay to metrics such as fork rate, transmission success, and throughput.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Calibrating the Performance and Security of Blockchains via Information Propagation Delays 2) DAG-Based Ledger for IoT: Performance and Security Analysis 3) Edge-Enabled Blockchain-Based V2X Scheme 4) Identifying Impacts of Protocol and Internet Development on the Bitcoin Network 5) Performance Analysis of Wireless PBFT Using IEEE 802.11 6) Taming Propagation Delay and Fork Rate in Bitcoin Mining Network 7) Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture 8) Bitcoin-NG: A Scalable Blockchain Protocol 9) Blockchain-based IAS Protocol in Cloud 10) Blockchain-based AMI Framework

Tabela 5: Metrics Catalog: Availability Level

Metric	Availability Level
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Availability
Definition	Probability that a blockchain service is operational and accessible when requested. This level depends on the reliability of the nodes, the infrastructure used, and the policies adopted for validation and consensus.
Objective	To evaluate and plan the continuity of the blockchain service, support the definition of service level agreements (SLAs), and compare different network configurations and validation policies in terms of their impact on interruptions and unavailability.
Equation	$A = \frac{MTTF}{MTTF + MTTR}$, where MTTF is the mean time to failure and MTTR is the mean time to repair. The average annual downtime can be estimated as $(1 - A) \times 8760$ hours.
Comment	Higher availability values indicate more reliable services with less downtime. In general, the higher the number of “nines” (e.g., 99.9% or 99.99%), the lower the annual downtime. The choice of architecture and validation policies directly influences this result.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clearly define what it means for the service to be available (e.g., transaction submission and confirmation). 2) Record failures and recovery times of system components. 3) Compute MTTF and MTTR from the collected data. 4) Estimate service availability and annual downtime. 5) Compare different network configurations and validation policies against SLA requirements.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A Model-Based Approach for Planning Blockchain Service Provisioning 2) A Privacy-Preserving Data Transfer in a Blockchain-Based Commercial Real Estate Platform

Tabela 6: Metrics Catalog: Energy Consumption

Metric	Energy Consumption
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of electrical energy consumed by a device, node, or blockchain system while performing a given function or over a period of time.
Objective	To evaluate the energy efficiency of blockchain-based systems, especially in scenarios involving IoT devices, smart grids, and resource-constrained environments.
Equation	$E = \int P(t) dt.$ In practice, consumption can be estimated as the sum of periodic power measurements multiplied by the sampling interval.
Comment	Lower energy consumption indicates higher efficiency for performing the same task. High values may impact operational costs, device autonomy, and system sustainability. It is recommended to observe high percentiles (p95 or p99) and energy per operation.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation period and the measurement frequency. 2) Instrument devices or nodes with energy sensors and synchronized clocks. 3) Collect power or energy readings over time. 4) Aggregate and store the data, preferably off-chain, with integrity records. 5) Compute total consumption and statistics such as mean and percentiles. 6) Relate consumption to operational events or executed functions.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A Data Analytics Scheme for Security-aware DRM in Smart Grid 2) Exploring Blockchain-Secured Data Validation in Smart Meter Readings 3) Integrating IoT and Blockchain for Mining Inspection Systems 4) Secure Data Exchange Between IoT Endpoints for Energy Balancing 5) Blockchain & MLR-based Energy Trading Scheme for EVs

Tabela 7: Metrics Catalog: Error Rate

Metric	Error Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of operations that fail relative to the total number of attempts in a blockchain system, such as rejected transactions, corrupted messages, or communication errors.
Objective	To evaluate the reliability of the system and its ability to handle failures, identifying issues related to network conditions, smart contract logic, or consensus configuration.
Equation	$\text{Error Rate} = \frac{\text{number of errors}}{\text{total number of attempts}}$ <p>Depending on the context, it may represent transaction failures, communication bit errors, or policy-based rejections.</p>
Comment	The lower the error rate, the better the system reliability. High values indicate instability, network problems, or logical failures. It is recommended to analyze high percentiles (p95 or p99) and distinguish communication errors from execution errors.
Scale Type	Proportion
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clearly define what will be considered an error (transaction failure, rejection, communication error). 2) Instrument clients and nodes to record attempts and failures. 3) Run tests under different loads, data sizes, and network configurations. 4) Compute the error rate over time windows and obtain statistics such as mean and percentiles. 5) Analyze the causes of errors and their relationship with other metrics, such as latency and throughput.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Blockchain-Based Secure Voting Mechanism Underlying 5G Network 2) LECDs With Blockchain for Enhanced Security on Cloud Server 3) Proof of Continuous Work 4) Privacy-Preserving E-Voting Supporting Score Voting 5) Secure Decentralized EHR Sharing

Tabela 8: Metrics Catalog: Execution Time

Attribute Name (Title)	Execution Time
Keywords / Alias	Processing time; Chaincode/contract execution time
Attribute Definition	Time interval required for the application/contract logic to execute from start to finish (from the call point to the completion of processing). In permissioned platforms (e.g., Hyperledger), this is typically measured as the <i>chaincode</i> execution time; in EVM-based systems, it can be associated with the execution time of the contract function (distinct from cost/gas).
Objective / Motivation	To evaluate the efficiency of the implementation and the <i>stack</i> (SDK, peers/validators, VM), and to guide code optimizations and architectural choices. Studies report <i>execution time</i> together with latency and throughput to compare frameworks/consensus mechanisms and demonstrate efficiency gains.
Domain Independence Level	Fully domain-independent (finance, IoT/IIoT, healthcare, supply chain, etc.).
Quality Model	ISO/IEC 25010
Characteristic	Performance
Subcharacteristic	Time behavior (processing time)
Equation	Execution Time = $T_{\text{end_exec}} - T_{\text{start_exec}}$. Examples: (a) <i>Chaincode</i> : from <i>invoke</i> to function completion; (b) <i>Smart contract</i> : from call submission to the <i>receipt</i> /on-chain completion event (when applicable).
Associated Metrics	Latency (end-to-end); Throughput (TPS); Communication overhead; Resource consumption (CPU/memory); Transaction cost (gas).
Related Attribute	Resource-use efficiency; Scalability; Confirmation reliability.

Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Precisely define the measurement points ($T_{\text{start_exec}}$, $T_{\text{end_exec}}$): at the client/SDK (call), at the peer/validator (start/end of <i>chaincode</i>), or via <i>event/receipt</i>. 2. Synchronize clocks (NTP/PTP) and record conditions (nodes, consensus, bandwidth, load). 3. Run controlled <i>workloads</i> varying: payload size, concurrency, consensus (PBFT/IBFT/Raft/PoW/PoS), and number of nodes. 4. Compute statistics (mean, median, p90/p95/p99) and correlate with latency and TPS. 5. Report communication/storage <i>overheads</i> and configurations (e.g., compression, <i>endorsement policy</i>).
Comment	In real-world scenarios, <i>execution time</i> is affected by state I/O and cryptographic overhead. Works in IIoT/Agri and healthcare measure <i>average execution time</i> together with gas cost/latency/throughput; off-chain solutions (e.g., IPFS) reduce costs and can improve perceived execution time at the contract layer.
Interpretation of Measured Value	Lower is better. Observe high percentiles (p95/p99) and stability under load; compare implementation/consensus variants and the effects of <i>batching</i> /block size.
Unit	Milliseconds (ms) or seconds (s).
Scale Type	Absolute
Precision	Depends on instrumentation (timestamp location) and synchronization; avoid confusing execution time (processing) with end-to-end latency (which includes network/consensus).
Data Collection Type	Automatic
Measurement Tool	Hyperledger Caliper (Fabric and similar benchmarks); Node.js/SDK instrumentation (time collection); explorers/events for <i>receipts</i> .
Potential Use Processes	Consensus/platform benchmarking; Contract/chaincode optimization; Capacity planning; SRE/Observability; Evaluation of timing requirements in IoT/healthcare/supply chain.
Potential Beneficiaries	Software/contract engineers; System architects; Operators/SRE; Product/SLA managers.

<p>References</p>	<p>(1) Nasir et al., <i>Performance Analysis of Hyperledger Fabric Platforms</i> — evaluates <i>execution time</i>, latency, and throughput in Fabric.</p> <p>(2) Kumar & Chand, <i>MedHypChain</i> — measures <i>execution time</i>, latency, and throughput in a permissioned healthcare network.</p> <p>(3) Deebak et al., <i>Lightweight Blockchain-Based Remote Mutual Authentication (B-RMA)</i> — uses Node.js and evaluates <i>execution time</i>, throughput, and overhead.</p> <p>(4) Chatterjee et al., <i>Blockchain-Enabled Security Framework for Smart Agriculture</i> — reports <i>average execution time</i>, gas cost, throughput, and latency.</p> <p>(5) Uddin et al., <i>From Hype to Reality—Blockchain in SCM</i> — compares solutions focusing on efficiency, <i>execution time</i>, security, and latency.</p> <p>(6) Bai et al., <i>GDPR-Compliant Data Storage and Sharing in Smart Healthcare</i> — discusses IPFS/Blockchain architectures and performance impacts.</p>
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Tabela 9: Metrics Catalog: Fairness

Metric	Fairness
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Degree of “fairness” in how network participants take part in block creation and in how information is received across the network. It typically evaluates whether a participant’s chance of producing blocks is proportional to its mining or validation power and whether all nodes receive blocks within similar time intervals.
Objective	To identify situations in which stronger or better-connected participants gain a disproportionate advantage, which may increase centralization, raise chain conflicts, and reduce system security.
Equation	One way to measure fairness is to compare the actual share of block production with the share expected from the participant’s mining or validation power. Another approach measures the difference between the average block reception times across nodes (the smaller the difference, the fairer the network).
Comment	Low fairness may indicate a tendency toward centralization and an advantage for large participants, especially in the presence of propagation delays, large blocks, or short block intervals. Improvements in network topology and propagation mechanisms can reduce inequalities and lower the fork rate.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define an observation period and collect the blocks included in the main chain. 2) Identify the producer of each block (miner or validator), when this information is available. 3) Compare the actual share of block production with the share expected from the participant’s power. 4) If propagation fairness is measured, instrument nodes to record block reception times and compare differences across nodes. 5) Record experimental conditions such as block size, block interval, and network parameters (RTT, bandwidth, and packet loss).
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Taming Propagation Delay and Fork Rate in Bitcoin Mining Network 2) Bitcoin-NG: A Scalable Blockchain Protocol

Tabela 10: Metrics Catalog: Gas Consumption

Metric	Gas Consumption
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of gas actually consumed to execute a function, transaction, or smart contract in an EVM-based blockchain. Gas consumption represents only the technical computational effort of the operation, independent of economic factors.
Objective	To evaluate the technical efficiency of smart contracts and on-chain operations, supporting code optimization and comparison between implementations without relying on gas price or network economic conditions.
Equation	Gas Consumption = <code>gasUsed</code> . Where <code>gasUsed</code> is the sum of the costs of the executed instructions during the operation. This value does not include <code>gasPrice</code> and does not represent monetary cost.
Comment	Lower gas consumption indicates higher on-chain computational efficiency. This metric is strictly technical and allows comparing the “weight” of execution across contracts or functions regardless of the financial amount paid. It is recommended to analyze high percentiles (p95/p99) and evaluate sensitivity to data size, number of participants, and state read/write patterns.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the functions or contracts to be evaluated, including deployment. 2) Execute the operations on a test network or controlled environment. 3) Collect the <code>gasUsed</code> value from transaction receipts. 4) Repeat the tests to obtain statistics such as mean and percentiles. 5) Compare different implementations or off-chain alternatives to reduce gas consumption.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Blockchain-Based Energy Trading Scheme for EVs 2) Blockchain-Based Secure Voting Mechanism Underlying 5G 3) Function-Level Dynamic Monitoring and Analysis System for Smart Contract 4) Application of Blockchain for Secure Data Transmission in Distributed State Estimation 5) Green Power Electricity Generation Devices Using Blockchain-Based Accent

Tabela 11: Metrics Catalog: Gas Cost

Metric	Gas Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of gas required by an operation in an EVM-based blockchain, used as the basis for estimating the economic cost of executing that operation when combined with the gas price.
Objective	To provide a baseline measure for estimating economic impact and comparing the potential financial “weight” of functions and contracts, supporting optimization decisions and operational cost planning.
Equation	Gas Cost (base) = <code>gasUsed</code> . The monetary cost can be estimated as: transaction cost = <code>gasUsed</code> × <code>gasPrice</code> .
Comment	Although measured in gas units, this “cost” represents the potential economic impact of an operation. Thus, two functions may have the same technical consumption, but the final monetary cost varies with <code>gasPrice</code> and network conditions. It is recommended to analyze high percentiles (p95/p99) and to distinguish deployment (deploy) costs from execution (call) costs.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the functions or contracts to be evaluated. 2) Execute the operations in a controlled environment or test network. 3) Collect the <code>gasUsed</code> value from the transaction receipt. 4) Repeat the tests to obtain statistics such as mean and percentiles. 5) When necessary, estimate the monetary cost by combining <code>gasUsed</code> with the measured <code>gasPrice</code>.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Empirically Analyzing Ethereum’s Gas Mechanism 2) Health-ID 3) Traceability Management System Using Blockchain Technology and Cost Estimation in the Metrology Field 4) Blockchain-Based Energy Trading Scheme for EVs 5) A Quality of Service Compliance System 6) BOSSA 7) Distributed Ledger for Spammers’ Resume

Tabela 12: Metrics Catalog: Latency

Metric	Latency
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Elapsed time between the submission of a transaction to the blockchain network and the moment it is considered confirmed according to the adopted policy.
Objective	To evaluate the response time perceived by users and applications, serving as a central indicator of responsiveness and suitability of the blockchain for time-sensitive scenarios.
Equation	Latency = confirmation time – transaction submission time.
Comment	Lower latency indicates more responsive systems. In public blockchains, latency may increase for transactions with low fees or under congestion. In permissioned networks, it tends to be lower but still depends on the number of nodes, the consensus mechanism, and the workload.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define what characterizes a confirmed transaction (e.g., block inclusion or a minimum number of confirmations). 2) Record the transaction submission time. 3) Record the time at which confirmation occurs. 4) Compute the difference between the two timestamps. 5) Analyze statistics such as mean, median, and percentiles (p95, p99) considering the test scenario.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) BitcoinF: Achieving Fairness for Bitcoin in Transaction-Fee-Only Model 2) Securing Data Exchange in IoT–Metaverse 3) A Blockchain Enabled Predictive, Analytical Model 4) A Quality of Service Compliance System 5) A Trustworthy Safety Inspection Framework Using Performance-Security Balanced Blockchain 6) Architecture and Performance Evaluation of Blockchain-Based Peer-to-Peer Energy Trading 7) An Edge Intelligent Blockchain-Based Reputation System for IIoT 8) Blockchain for IoT: A Consensus Mechanism Analysis 9) Decentralized Blockchain-Based and Trust-Aware Task Offloading Strategy for Healthcare IoT

Tabela 13: Metrics Catalog: Ledger Size

Metric	Ledger Size
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Total amount of storage space occupied by the blockchain's persisted data on a node. This includes blocks (headers, transactions, and receipts) and, when applicable, the network's global state (world state).
Objective	To evaluate blockchain storage consumption over time, support scalability analysis, and compare design choices such as fully on-chain storage versus off-chain solutions with cryptographic anchoring.
Equation	<p>The ledger size at time t corresponds to the total space occupied by blockchain data at that moment: $L(t) = \text{block data size} + \text{state size}$.</p> <p>Ledger growth over an observation period is the difference between final and initial sizes: $\text{Growth} = L(t_1) - L(t_0)$.</p> <p>Average growth per transaction indicates how much each transaction contributes, on average, to storage increase: $\text{Growth per transaction} = (L(t_1) - L(t_0)) / \text{number of transactions recorded in the period}$.</p>
Comment	In practice, this metric shows how fast the blockchain grows on disk over time. Workloads with many on-chain writes cause rapid ledger growth, increasing storage costs and harming scalability. Strategies such as data aggregation, periodic anchoring, and off-chain storage (with only hashes anchored on-chain) significantly reduce ledger growth.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the analysis period and the type of node evaluated (full, archive, or pruned). 2) Measure the total size of persisted data on the node at the beginning (t_0) and at the end (t_1) of the period. 3) Obtain the number of blocks and transactions recorded in the same interval. 4) Compute total ledger growth and average growth per transaction. 5) Record environment parameters such as block size, block interval, batching policy, and use of off-chain storage.

References	1) Distributed Ledger for Spammers' Resume 2) Fast Policy Interpretation and Dynamic Conflict Resolution for Blockchain-Based IoT System
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Tabela 14: Metrics Catalog: Number of Transactions

Metric	Number of Transactions
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of transactions processed by the blockchain over a given period of time.
Objective	To evaluate the volume of operations that the system can process and to support capacity, scalability, and demand analyses.
Equation	The number of transactions in a period is the simple count of all transactions that occurred between two time instants. This value can be used to estimate throughput (TPS) by dividing the number of transactions by the observed time.
Comment	A high number of transactions indicates greater system usage. However, this value should be analyzed together with metrics such as latency and throughput to verify whether the blockchain can maintain stable performance under load.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	1) Define the analysis period. 2) Choose the data source (local node or block explorer). 3) Count the number of transactions recorded during the period. 4) Relate the observed volume to performance metrics such as TPS and latency.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Framework for IoT Data Monetization Services 2) Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain for II-oMT 3) Performance Evaluation of M/D/1 Queuing Model on Hyperledger Fabric 4) A Blockchain-Based Trust Management Framework with Verifiable Interactions 5) Improving Data Access Control Using Blockchain for Healthcare Domain

Tabela 15: Metrics Catalog: Operational Cost

Metric	Operational Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Total cost to keep a blockchain application or network running over time, considering both on-chain costs (transaction fees and contract execution) and off-chain infrastructure costs such as processing, storage, networking, and energy.
Objective	To evaluate the financial impact of operating blockchain-based solutions, supporting architectural decisions, contract optimization, off-chain storage usage, and budget planning.
Equation	Operational Cost = sum of on-chain fees ($\text{gasUsed} \times \text{gasPrice}$) + infrastructure costs + energy costs, measured over a defined period.
Comment	Operational cost reflects the combined effect of technical and market decisions. Higher gas prices tend to reduce confirmation time but increase cost. Strategies such as IPFS usage, operation aggregation, and proper consensus parameter choices help reduce total cost without compromising SLAs.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the analysis period and the reference currency (e.g., ETH or USD). 2) Collect <code>gasUsed</code> and <code>gasPrice</code> values for each transaction. 3) Compute on-chain cost by summing $\text{gasUsed} \times \text{gasPrice}$ over the period. 4) Add infrastructure and energy costs from the execution environment. 5) Compute aggregate metrics such as total cost and average cost per transaction. 6) Compare scenarios (on-chain vs. off-chain, different gas policies, or architectures).
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Distributed Network Slicing Management Using Blockchains in E-Health Environments 2) A Quality of Service Compliance System Empowered by Smart Contracts and Oracles

Tabela 16: Metrics Catalog: Gas Price

Metric	Gas Price
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Monetary value paid per unit of gas for a transaction or smart contract execution to be included and processed on the blockchain. In EVM-based networks, this value reflects competition for the network's computational resources.
Objective	To evaluate the economic impact of transaction prioritization and to support cost-versus-confirmation-time decisions, assisting financial planning and SLA definition.
Equation	Effective gas price (EIP-1559): $\text{gasPrice} = \min(\text{maxFee}, \text{baseFee} + \text{priorityFee})$. Transaction cost = $\text{gasUsed} \times \text{gasPrice}$.
Comment	Higher gas prices increase the likelihood of fast transaction inclusion but raise monetary cost. Lower prices reduce cost but may lead to higher latency. This metric should be analyzed together with gas consumption and latency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Define the network and the observation period. 2) Collect <code>baseFee</code> , <code>priorityFee</code> , <code>maxFee</code> , and effective gas price per transaction via a node or explorer. 3) Compute gas price statistics (mean, median, p95/p99). 4) Relate observed values to confirmation times and network congestion.
References	1) Traceability Management System Using Blockchain Technology and Cost Estimation in the Metrology Field 2) A Blockchain-Based Framework for IoT Data Monetization Services

Tabela 17: Metrics Catalog: Processing Time

Metric	Processing Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time spent executing the computational processing of an operation, function, or validation, considering only the internal work performed by the node or device (e.g., contract execution, cryptographic verification, or local validation), excluding network delays and consensus waiting time.
Objective	To evaluate the internal computational efficiency of nodes, smart contracts, or edge devices, supporting code optimization, platform selection, and resource provisioning.
Equation	Processing Time = $T_{\text{end}} - T_{\text{start}}$. Optionally: Processing Time = $T_{\text{queue}} + T_{\text{exec}}$.
Comment	Lower values indicate higher computational efficiency. Analysis should prioritize high percentiles (p95/p99) to identify degradation under load, concurrency, or hardware constraints. Unlike latency, this metric does not include network or consensus delays.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clearly define the scope of the measured processing (local execution, validation, cryptography). 2) Instrument timestamps at the beginning and end of processing. 3) Run tests under different loads and input sizes. 4) Collect multiple samples and compute statistics (mean, median, p95/p99). 5) Record the experimental context (hardware, platform, concurrency).
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Exploring Blockchain-Secured Data Validation in Smart Meter Readings 2) A Blockchain-Based Approach Using Proof of Continuous Work 3) Integrating IoT and Blockchain Technology for the Next Generation of Mining Inspection Systems 4) LBSS: A Lightweight Blockchain-Based Security Scheme for IoT-Enabled Healthcare Environment 5) Smart Microgrid Energy Market: Evaluating Distributed Ledger Technologies for Remote and Constrained Microgrid Deployments

Tabela 18: Metrics Catalog: Propagation Time

Metric	Propagation Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for information to spread across the blockchain network, from the node that originated the block (or transaction) to the other nodes. In practice, it measures how long it takes for a relevant fraction of the network to receive and recognize the block.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of network communication and understand how propagation affects events such as forks (competing blocks), security, and performance. This metric helps guide decisions on parameters such as block interval and block size.
Equation	Propagation Time = $T_{\text{arrival}} - T_{\text{origin}}$. It can also be analyzed using percentiles such as p50, p90, p95, and p99, representing the time required to reach a fraction of the network.
Comment	Lower propagation time is better. If propagation is slow relative to the block interval, the likelihood of forks increases. High percentiles (p95/p99) are particularly important because they reveal delays under congestion.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define what will be measured (block or transaction propagation) and which percentiles will be analyzed (p50, p90, p95, p99). 2) Ensure time synchronization among measurement nodes (e.g., NTP) to enable timestamp comparison. 3) Instrument nodes to record T_{origin} (when the block is announced/created) and T_{arrival} (when each node receives/validates it). 4) Compute propagation times and generate statistics (mean, median, and percentiles), and correlate with forks when applicable. 5) Record test conditions (network topology, bandwidth/RTT, block size, block interval, and relay mechanisms) and compare scenarios.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Block Interval Adjustment Based on Block Propagation Time in a Blockchain 2) Taming Propagation Delay and Fork Rate in Bitcoin Mining Network 3) A Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture Based on a Secure OpenFlow Protocol Controller Channel 4) Health-ID

Tabela 19: Metrics Catalog: Resource Utilization

Metric	Resource Utilization
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Degree of usage of computational and infrastructure resources of a blockchain system, such as CPU, memory, storage, and network, during transaction execution, block validation, and smart contract execution.
Objective	To evaluate the operational efficiency of blockchain systems, identifying how different architectures (on-chain and hybrid with off-chain storage) and consensus mechanisms influence resource consumption and system scalability.
Equation	$UR = (\text{sum of CPU, memory, network, and storage consumption}) / \text{observation}$
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain system in a controlled environment. 2) Define representative workloads (e.g., record creation, update, and query). 3) Run experiments under different transaction volumes. 4) Monitor CPU, memory, network, and storage usage of the nodes. 5) Compute average utilization and peak values for each resource. 6) Compare results between fully on-chain architectures and hybrid solutions.
Comment	Lower resource utilization indicates higher system efficiency. Studies show that using off-chain storage such as IPFS significantly reduces CPU and on-chain storage consumption, keeping only hashes and metadata on-chain. Permissioned architectures tend to exhibit more controlled resource usage compared to public blockchains.
Scale Type	Ratio
References	1) Hyperledger Healthchain: Patient-Centric IPFS-Based Storage of Health Records

Tabela 20: Metrics Catalog: Response Time

Metric	Response Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Elapsed time between the moment a request is sent by a client and the instant when the corresponding response is received. In blockchain systems, this time may include validation, execution, ordering, and confirmation, depending on the type of operation.
Objective	To evaluate how quickly the system responds to user requests, supporting performance analysis, infrastructure sizing, and SLA definition for time-sensitive applications.
Equation	Response Time = $T_{\text{response}} - T_{\text{request}}$. The metric is typically analyzed using percentiles (p50, p95, p99) to capture average behavior and peaks under concurrency.
Comment	Lower response times indicate higher system responsiveness. High percentiles (p95/p99) are critical for identifying delays under load and assessing whether the system meets application time requirements.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the evaluated operation (query or transaction). 2) Instrument the client to record request and response timestamps. 3) Run tests under different concurrency levels and data sizes. 4) Compute the response time distribution (mean, p50, p95, p99). 5) Record system parameters (consensus, block size, and block interval) and compare scenarios.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) T-DSES: A Blockchain-Powered Trusted Decentralized Service Eco-System 2) A Blockchain-Based Approach Using Proof of Continuous Work 3) A Blockchain-Enabled Approach for Enhancing Synchronphasor Measurement in Smart Grid 3.0

Tabela 21: Metrics Catalog: Storage Cost

Metric	Storage Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Monetary cost associated with storing data on a blockchain, primarily considering on-chain write operations and the gas price required to keep this data permanently recorded.
Objective	To evaluate the economic impact of data storage in blockchain-based solutions and to support architectural decisions such as storing data directly on-chain or using off-chain storage with hash anchoring.
Equation	Storage Cost = $\text{gasUsedForWrite} \times \text{gasPrice}$. In EVM-based blockchains, writing data to the state consumes gas proportional to the stored volume and can be estimated per word or per kilobyte.
Comment	High costs indicate that on-chain storage may become economically unfeasible for large data volumes. Strategies that store only hashes on-chain and keep the content off-chain, such as IPFS, significantly reduce costs with minimal impact on data integrity.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define which data will be stored directly on-chain and which can be kept off-chain. 2) Measure the gas consumed by data write operations in the smart contract. 3) Obtain the average gas price during the analyzed period. 4) Compute the cost per unit of stored data (e.g., per word or per kilobyte). 5) Compare fully on-chain storage with hybrid architectures using IPFS or similar solutions.
References	1) ET-DeaL: A P2P Smart Contract-Based Secure Energy Trading Scheme for Smart Grid Systems

Tabela 22: Metrics Catalog: Storage Overhead

Metric	Storage Overhead
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of additional data stored by a blockchain-based solution beyond the actual useful content. This overhead includes metadata, headers, indexes, internal state, anchoring hashes, control information, and replication data.
Objective	To evaluate the impact of design decisions on storage usage, especially when comparing fully on-chain approaches with hybrid architectures that store only references or hashes on the blockchain.
Equation	Absolute Overhead = Total Stored Data – Useful Content. Percentage Overhead = (Absolute Overhead / Useful Content) × 100.
Comment	High values indicate inefficient storage usage, since a large fraction of space is consumed by auxiliary information. Solutions that store only metadata or hashes on-chain and keep the actual content off-chain tend to significantly reduce overhead without compromising data integrity or auditability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Define the evaluated scenario (fully on-chain storage or hybrid architecture). 2) Measure the total volume of data stored during the analyzed period. 3) Measure separately the size of the useful content. 4) Compute absolute and percentage overhead. 5) Compare results across different architectures or storage strategies.
References	1) AAC-IoT: Attribute Access Control Scheme for IoT Using Lightweight Cryptography and Hyperledger Fabric 2) Education Evaluation Management Based on Blockchain Technology

Tabela 23: Metrics Catalog: Fork Rate

Metric	Fork Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of blocks that are created but do not remain in the main blockchain. These blocks, called stale or orphaned blocks, arise when two or more valid blocks are produced almost simultaneously and only one is accepted as the official continuation of the chain.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of block propagation and the robustness of the consensus protocol, identifying wasted computational effort and risks to network stability.
Equation	$\text{Fork Rate} = N_{\text{stale}} / (N_{\text{stale}} + N_{\text{main}}) \times 100.$
Comment	High fork rates indicate that blocks take too long to propagate through the network, increasing competition among block producers. This leads to wasted resources and can weaken security. Sustained reductions in fork rate usually reflect real improvements in propagation protocols, network topology, or block parameters.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network and the observation window. 2) Identify all blocks produced during the period. 3) Classify which blocks remained in the main chain and which became stale. 4) Count N_{stale} and N_{main}. 5) Apply the fork rate formula and analyze its evolution over time.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identifying Impacts of Protocol and Internet Development on the Bitcoin Network 2) Taming Propagation Delay and Fork Rate in Bitcoin Mining Network

Tabela 24: Metrics Catalog: Throughput

Metric	Throughput
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Number of transactions that the blockchain correctly confirms within a given time interval. Throughput indicates the practical capacity of the system to process operations without forming excessive queues.
Objective	To evaluate the processing capacity of the blockchain network and compare different consensus configurations, block parameters, and architectures under controlled load.
Equation	Throughput = $N_{\text{confirmed transactions}}/\Delta t$.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater processing capacity but must be analyzed together with latency. Increasing throughput at the cost of excessive confirmation delays can harm user experience and perceived reliability. Stable throughput across different load levels indicates a more scalable and well-provisioned system.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation interval (Δt) and the adopted confirmation criterion. 2) Submit a known transaction load to the network. 3) Count the number of transactions actually confirmed within Δt. 4) Compute throughput using the defined equation. 5) Repeat the experiment under different loads and configurations for comparison.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Architecture and Performance Evaluation of Blockchain-Based P2P Energy Trading 2) Edge-Intelligent Blockchain-Based Reputation System for IIoT 3) B4SDC: A Blockchain System for Security Data Collection in MANETs 4) BENIGREEN: Blockchain-Based Energy-Efficient Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Green IoT 5) Edge-Enabled Blockchain-Based V2X Scheme 6) How Much Communication Resource is Needed to Run a Wireless Blockchain Network? 7) A Quality of Service Compliance System

Tabela 25: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Cost

Metric	Transaction Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Economic cost paid to the blockchain protocol for a transaction to be executed and included in a block. In EVM-based blockchains, this cost is determined by the transaction's gas consumption and the effective gas price at execution time.
Objective	To quantify the economic cost associated with executing on-chain transactions, enabling evaluation of computational resource efficiency, comparison of blockchain platforms, and support for smart contract optimization.
Equation	Transaction Cost = $\text{gasUsed} \times \text{effectiveGasPrice}$, where $\text{effectiveGasPrice} = \text{BaseFee} + \text{PriorityFee}$.
Comment	Lower values indicate higher economic efficiency in the use of blockchain resources. Analysis should consider gas price variability under different network conditions, and it is recommended to evaluate statistics such as the median and high percentiles (p95/p99) in congestion scenarios.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the set of on-chain transactions or functions to be evaluated. 2) Measure <code>gasUsed</code> for each transaction using development tools or block explorers. 3) Record the <code>effectiveGasPrice</code> at execution time. 4) Compute the transaction cost as $\text{gasUsed} \times \text{effectiveGasPrice}$. 5) Report descriptive statistics (median, p95) and convert values to the desired currency.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Traceability Management System Using Blockchain Technology and Cost Estimation in the Metrology Field 2) Towards a Smarter IoT Environment with EVM Enabling Ledgers 3) Blockchain-Based Energy Trading Scheme for EVs 4) Blockchain for Giving Patients Control Over Their Medical Records 5) MRBSCchain (BSC)

Tabela 26: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Fee

Metric	Transaction Fee
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount paid for a transaction or smart contract execution to be processed and included in a blockchain block. In EVM-compatible platforms, the fee depends on the gas consumed by the operation and the gas price at execution time.
Objective	To evaluate the economic cost of executing on-chain transactions, supporting feasibility analysis, budgeting, definition of recording policies, and assessment of financial impact on users and applications.
Equation	Transaction Fee = $\text{gasUsed} \times \text{gasPrice}$. Optionally, in fiat currency: Fee (fiat) = Fee (crypto) \times cryptocurrency exchange rate.
Comment	Higher fees indicate greater cost to execute operations on the blockchain. During congestion periods, increases in gas price raise the fee even without changes in technical consumption. Simple transactions tend to have lower fees, while contract calls and data writes significantly increase the amount paid.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network and the observation period. 2) Collect gasUsed and gasPrice for each transaction. 3) Compute the individual fee using the defined equation. 4) Aggregate results by operation type and compute statistics (mean and percentiles). 5) Compare fully on-chain usage scenarios with architectures using off-chain data.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Distributed Network Slicing Management Using Blockchains in E-Health Environments 2) Smart Microgrid Energy Market: Evaluating Distributed Ledger Technologies for Remote and Constrained Microgrid Deployments

Tabela 27: Metrics Catalog: Transactions per Second

Metric	Transactions per Second (TPS)
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Average number of transactions that a blockchain can confirm per second within a defined time interval. This metric expresses the practical processing capacity of the network under given load and configuration conditions.
Objective	To evaluate the blockchain’s processing capacity and verify whether the platform meets the transaction volume requirements of a system or application, supporting comparisons across protocols, consensus parameters, and architectures.
Equation	General definition: $\text{TPS} = N_{\text{confirmed tx}} / \Delta t.$ In PoW blockchains: $\text{TPS} \approx (1 - R_{\text{stale}}) \times (N_{\text{tx per block}} / T_{\text{block}}),$ where R_{stale} is the fraction of stale blocks, $N_{\text{tx per block}}$ is the average number of transactions per block, and T_{block} is the average block time.
Comment	Higher TPS values indicate greater processing capacity. However, artificial increases (such as excessively reducing block time) may raise the fork rate and harm reliability. In permissioned networks or sharded systems, TPS can increase significantly without the same trade-offs observed in PoW-based public blockchains.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation window (Δt) and the confirmation criterion (main chain). 2) Count only transactions that are effectively confirmed during the period. 3) Compute the average TPS by dividing the total number of confirmed transactions by the observed time. 4) Record relevant parameters: block time, block size, gas limit, number of nodes/validators, and consensus mechanism. 5) Repeat measurements under different loads to compare stability and capacity.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Assessing Blockchain Selfish Mining in an Imperfect Network 2) A Dynamic Sharding Protocol Design for Consortium Blockchains 3) Health-ID: A Blockchain-Based Decentralized Identity 4) Blockchain and Machine Learning for Ride-Hailing Systems

Tabela 28: Metrics Catalog: Summary Information Accuracy

Metric	Summary Information Accuracy
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Correctness
Definition	Degree to which the metadata and data summaries recorded on the blockchain correctly represent the actual content of the data stored off-chain. This metric indicates whether the on-chain summary (such as data type, volume, and hash) faithfully corresponds to the dataset that is effectively provided.
Objective	To ensure that the summarized information recorded on-chain is trustworthy and matches the real data, fostering trust between data providers and consumers in decentralized data trading systems and preventing fraud or misleading representations.
Equation	Summary Accuracy = $EUID(1)_i$, with values in the range $[0, 1]$, where 1 indicates full correspondence between the blockchain-registered summary and the actual data, and values close to 0 indicate inconsistencies.
Comment	In blockchain-based data trading systems, only summaries and hashes are stored on-chain, while full datasets remain off-chain. This metric is essential to verify whether what is advertised on the blockchain truly reflects the delivered data, supporting reputation, payment, and automated penalty mechanisms.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The provider records a data summary on the blockchain containing metadata and a cryptographic hash. 2) The consumer accesses the actual data stored off-chain. 3) The system compares the registered summary with the real content using cryptographic validation. 4) The correspondence is converted into a normalized score between 0 and 1. 5) The obtained value is recorded for auditing and provider reputation purposes.
References	1) A Blockchain-based Trading System for Big Data

Tabela 29: Metrics Catalog: Age of Information

Metric	Age of Information
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behaviour
Definition	Elapsed time from when a piece of information is generated until the current moment when it becomes available for use. In blockchain-based systems, it represents how long data takes from collection to confirmation and recording on the ledger, indicating how fresh or outdated the accessible information is.
Objective	To evaluate the freshness of information in blockchain systems, especially in time-sensitive applications such as IoT, healthcare, and industrial control, where outdated data may compromise decisions and operations.
Equation	$AoI(t) = t - u(t),$ <p>where t is the current time and $u(t)$ is the time of the last confirmed update.</p> <p>The total delay can be decomposed as: $t_i = T_s + T_{tx} + T_{tp} + T_{BC}$, with T_s (sensing), T_{tx} (transmission), T_{tp} (propagation), and T_{BC} (blockchain processing).</p>
Comment	Lower Age of Information values indicate fresher data and higher temporal efficiency. In blockchains, consensus, block propagation, and forks increase information age. Continuous growth in AoI reveals bottlenecks such as slow block production, network congestion, or low update frequency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the data generation time at the source device. 2) Measure the time until the data is confirmed and recorded on the blockchain. 3) Compute Age of Information as the difference between the current time and the time of the last valid update. 4) Repeat the measurement under different loads and consensus configurations. 5) Compare the obtained values to evaluate the impact of parameters such as block time, mining rate, and fork probability.
References	1) Analysis on the AoI in Blockchain-based IoT Networks with Different Sensing Mechanisms

Tabela 30: Metrics Catalog: Anonymity Level

Metric	Anonymity Level
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Confidentiality
Definition	Degree to which a participant's real identity cannot be linked to their transactions or actions recorded on a blockchain. The higher the anonymity, the harder it is to identify who performed a given operation.
Objective	To evaluate the protection of participants' identities in blockchain applications, especially in scenarios such as electronic auctions, where revealing identities may lead to manipulation, unfair advantages, or loss of fairness.
Equation	<p>A simple way to measure anonymity is the size of the anonymity set:</p> $A = S_0 /N,$ <p>where S_0 is the set of participants that are indistinguishable from each other and N is the total number of participants.</p> <p>Alternatively, Shannon entropy can be used:</p> $H = - \sum p_i \log_2(p_i),$ <p>where p_i is the probability of a participant being identified.</p>
Comment	Higher values indicate stronger identity protection, as many participants become indistinguishable from each other. In sealed-bid blockchain-based auction systems, techniques such as cryptographic commitments and zero-knowledge proofs increase anonymity by hiding bids and identities, reducing the risk of tracking, address correlation, or inference through usage patterns.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Record transactions pseudonymously using addresses or public keys. 2) Group transactions and participants to identify indistinguishable sets. 3) Compute the size of the anonymity set or the associated entropy. 4) Compare values across different privacy configurations. 5) Evaluate the impact of additional cryptographic mechanisms such as zero-knowledge proofs.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof

Tabela 31: Metrics Catalog: Anonymity Loss

Metric	Anonymity Loss
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Confidentiality
Definition	Degree to which a user or entity loses anonymity in a blockchain system when addresses, transactions, or usage patterns become linkable to a real-world identity. It reflects how much a participant ceases to be indistinguishable within the network.
Objective	To evaluate the risk of user re-identification in blockchain ecosystems, especially when there is dependence on centralized services, transaction correlation, or exposure of metadata that weakens privacy.
Equation	Anonymity loss can be expressed as: $LA = 1 - S_u / S_0 $, where S_0 is the initial set of indistinguishable users (ideal anonymity) and S_u is the remaining set after analysis. Alternatively: $P_{\text{reid}} = N_{\text{linked}}/N_{\text{total}}$, where N_{linked} is the number of re-identified entities and N_{total} is the total analyzed.
Comment	Low values indicate that users remain difficult to distinguish from each other, preserving anonymity. High values indicate higher re-identification risk, typically caused by repeated usage patterns, transaction graph analysis, or reliance on centralized services such as exchanges, custodial wallets, or API providers.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Define the scope of analysis (addresses, transactions, or services). 2) Collect on-chain data and identify relationships between transactions. 3) Apply address-linking or clustering heuristics. 4) Compute the residual anonymity set (S_u). 5) Estimate anonymity loss using LA or the re-identification probability.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 32: Metrics Catalog: Authentication Level

Metric	Authentication Level
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Authenticity
Definition	Degree to which a blockchain system can verify that users, nodes, or contracts interacting with the network are legitimate. It measures the effectiveness of cryptographic mechanisms used to confirm digital identities without revealing real-world identities.
Objective	To evaluate the blockchain system's ability to ensure that only properly authenticated entities perform valid operations, preventing identity spoofing and unauthorized access without relying on a central authority.
Equation	Authentication Level can be computed as: $AL = N_{\text{auth_success}}/N_{\text{auth_total}}$, where $N_{\text{auth_success}}$ is the number of successful authentications (valid signatures) and $N_{\text{auth_total}}$ is the total number of authentication attempts. Alternatively, individual authentication is verified by: $\text{Verify}(M, \text{Sig}, PK) \rightarrow \text{true or false}$.
Comment	High values indicate that most network interactions are performed by correctly authenticated entities, reflecting strong use of digital signatures and cryptographic keys. Low values suggest verification failures, compromised keys, or vulnerabilities in the authentication logic of smart contracts.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Assign each participant a public-private key pair. 2) Require every transaction or action to include a valid digital signature. 3) Automatically verify signatures in the smart contract. 4) Record successful and failed authentications. 5) Compute the authentication level as the ratio of valid authentications to total attempts.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof

Tabela 33: Metrics Catalog: Authentication Time

Metric	Authentication Time
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Authenticity
Definition	Time required to confirm the identity of an entity (user, device, or node) in a blockchain system, measured from the moment the authentication request is sent until the identity is successfully confirmed.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal efficiency of the authentication process in blockchain systems, ensuring that identity verification is secure and fast enough for time-sensitive applications such as industrial and medical IoT.
Equation	The average authentication time can be computed as: $T_{\text{auth}} = (1/N) \times \sum(t_{\text{confirm},i} - t_{\text{request},i}),$ where $t_{\text{request},i}$ is the time when the authentication request is sent and $t_{\text{confirm},i}$ is the time when the identity is confirmed by the system. In some scenarios, this time can be decomposed into cryptographic verification and blockchain validation.
Comment	Shorter times indicate more efficient authentication and better suitability for systems that require rapid response. High values may indicate network overload, complex cryptographic validation, or consensus delays, affecting system scalability and availability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Define the authentication scenario (user, device, or node). 2) Record the time when the authentication request is sent. 3) Record the time when the identity is confirmed. 4) Repeat the process for multiple authentications under different loads and network conditions. 5) Compute the average authentication time and analyze its stability.
References	1) A Novel Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Industrial Internet of Medical Things

Tabela 34: Metrics Catalog: Available Time

Metric	Available Time
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Availability
Definition	Proportion of time during which a blockchain node or service remains accessible and operational over an observation period. It indicates how long the system was effectively available to process transactions, execute smart contracts, or participate in consensus.
Objective	To evaluate the operational reliability of the blockchain infrastructure, identifying the system's ability to maintain continuous operation over time. This metric is especially relevant in critical systems, such as industrial and medical applications, where interruptions directly affect data delivery and processing.
Equation	$A_t = T_{\text{up}} / (T_{\text{up}} + T_{\text{down}})$, where T_{up} is the total time the node or service was available and T_{down} is the total downtime during the analyzed period.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater system stability and readiness. Frequent or prolonged periods of unavailability reduce available time and can compromise the reliability of applications that depend on continuous operation.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation period. 2) Continuously monitor the status of blockchain nodes or services. 3) Record the intervals during which the system was operational (T_{up}). 4) Record failure or downtime intervals (T_{down}). 5) Compute the ratio between available time and the total time of the period.
References	1) A Novel Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Industrial Internet of Medical Things

Tabela 35: Metrics Catalog: Bit Error Rate

Metric	Bit Error Rate (BER)
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of bits received incorrectly relative to the total number of bits transmitted over a communication channel. In blockchain systems integrated with 5G networks, this metric indicates the reliability of data transmission between devices, network nodes, and consensus services.
Objective	To evaluate the quality of the communication channel used by blockchain systems in 5G environments, verifying whether transmitted data arrives without corruption. This metric is especially important in sensitive applications such as electronic voting, where transmission errors may compromise transaction validity.
Equation	$BER = N_{\text{erroneous bits}}/N_{\text{total bits}}$, where $N_{\text{erroneous bits}}$ is the number of bits received incorrectly and $N_{\text{total bits}}$ is the total number of bits transmitted.
Comment	Lower values indicate more reliable communication and less need for retransmissions. High bit error rates increase delays, resource consumption, and the risk of failures in the synchronization of blockchain messages and transactions.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the communication channel to be evaluated. 2) Transmit a known data stream between devices and network nodes. 3) Record transmitted and received bits. 4) Count incorrectly received bits. 5) Compute the bit error rate as the ratio between erroneous and total bits.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Voting Mechanism Underlying 5G Network

Tabela 36: Metrics Catalog: Block Coverage

Metric	Block Coverage
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Proportion of blocks that can be observed or recorded by a set of nodes or block explorers relative to the total number of blocks actually produced by the blockchain network over a given period. This metric indicates how accurately the observed blockchain reflects the real block chain.
Objective	To evaluate the completeness and reliability of data collected by block explorers and monitoring nodes. This metric is important for empirical studies and audits, since gaps in observation may compromise analyses of performance, security, and network behavior.
Equation	$C_{\text{block}} = N_{\text{observed}}/N_{\text{total}}$, where N_{observed} is the number of blocks detected by explorers or measurement nodes and N_{total} is the actual number of blocks produced by the network during the same interval.
Comment	High values indicate that blocks produced by the network are being observed almost completely. Low values reveal visibility gaps, propagation delays, or data collection limitations, which may distort results of measurements and analyses based on public data.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Select block explorers or distributed nodes for monitoring. 2) Record all visible blocks during a defined time interval. 3) Estimate the total number of blocks produced in the period by comparing multiple reliable sources. 4) Compute the ratio between observed and produced blocks. 5) Repeat the measurement across different networks or exploration tools for comparison.
References	1) Behind Block Explorers: Public Blockchain Measurement and Security Implication

Tabela 37: Metrics Catalog: Block Delivery Time

Metric	Block Delivery Time
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Time Behaviour
Definition	Time required for a newly generated block to be propagated through the blockchain network and received by participating nodes. This metric expresses how fast information about a new block spreads across the network.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of block propagation and its impact on the consistency of the distributed ledger. Fast block delivery helps reduce forks, improve transaction confirmation times, and maintain stable consensus in blockchain networks.
Equation	$T_{\text{delivery}} = T_{\text{receive}} - T_{\text{generate}},$ <p>where T_{generate} is the time when the block is generated and T_{receive} is the time when the block is received by a node.</p> <p>The average value can be obtained as:</p> $T_{\text{delivery,avg}} = (1/N) \times \sum(T_{\text{receive},i} - T_{\text{generate},i}).$
Comment	Lower values indicate efficient propagation and good connectivity among network nodes. High values reveal communication delays, large block sizes, or poor connectivity, increasing the risk of forks and transaction confirmation delays.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select a set of distributed nodes in the blockchain network. 2) Record the time when each block is generated. 3) Measure the time when the block is received by each node. 4) Compute the delivery time for each observation. 5) Compute the average delivery time across a set of blocks.
References	1) Effect of Miner Incentive on the Confirmation Time of Bitcoin Transactions

Tabela 38: Metrics Catalog: Block Update Limit

Metric	Block Update Limit
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Maximum number of data updates that a blockchain can record in a block or across the chain within a given time interval without causing significant performance degradation or loss of integrity.
Objective	To evaluate the blockchain's ability to handle frequent data updates. This metric is particularly relevant for applications with continuous events, such as drone monitoring and smart cities, where information must be recorded quickly and reliably.
Equation	$L_{\text{update}} = N_{\text{update}}/T_{\text{interval}}$, where N_{update} is the number of updates confirmed on the blockchain during the observation period T_{interval} . The practical limit is defined as the highest value of L_{update} that keeps latency and consensus stable.
Comment	A higher update limit indicates that the network can process many changes without excessive delays. When this limit is exceeded, congestion, increased latency, and block validation failures may occur, compromising system reliability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation time interval. 2) Submit data update operations to the blockchain. 3) Record the number of updates confirmed during the period. 4) Compute the ratio between confirmed updates and observed time. 5) Evaluate the impact of increasing the update rate on latency and consensus.
References	1) A Trust-Based Mechanism for Drones in Smart Cities

Tabela 39: Metrics Catalog: Blockchain Fork Rate

Metric	Blockchain Fork Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of blocks that result in forks relative to the total number of blocks mined in the blockchain network. A fork occurs when different nodes temporarily maintain divergent versions of the blockchain.
Objective	To assess the stability of the consensus mechanism and the reliability of the blockchain network. A high fork rate indicates block propagation delays, network latency, or excessive mining concentration, which reduce the efficient use of network resources.
Equation	$F_{\text{rate}} = \frac{N_{\text{fork}}}{N_{\text{total}}},$ <p>where N_{fork} is the number of blocks that resulted in forks and N_{total} is the total number of blocks mined during the observation period.</p>
Comment	Low fork rates indicate good synchronization among nodes and stable consensus. High fork rates represent wasted computational effort, increased probability of chain reorganizations, and reduced overall blockchain efficiency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain observation period. 2) Record all blocks mined during the period. 3) Identify valid blocks that do not belong to the main chain. 4) Count the number of forked blocks. 5) Compute the ratio between forked blocks and total mined blocks.
References	1) Impact of GeoDistribution and Mining Pools on Blockchains: A Study of Ethereum

Tabela 40: Metrics Catalog: Blockchain Health Index

Metric	Blockchain Health Index
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Availability
Definition	Measures the overall operational state of a blockchain by combining security, performance, and economic stability. The index reflects whether the network is mostly maintained by honest participants, whether transactions are processed in a timely manner, and whether the fees required for block inclusion remain stable over time.
Objective	To assess whether the blockchain operates in a reliable and sustainable manner, especially in scenarios where the network relies primarily on transaction fees to incentivize miners. The metric helps detect imbalances that may compromise availability, such as increased latency, economic instability, or reduced honest mining participation.
Equation	$BHI = f(P_h, L_p, V_c)$, where P_h is the proportion of honest computational power, L_p is the average transaction processing latency, and V_c is the variance of the minimum required transaction fees.
Comment	The Blockchain Health Index summarizes the balance between security, performance, and economic stability. In mature networks, exclusive reliance on transaction fees may reduce honest participation and increase latency. Mechanisms that enforce minimum fee rules and fair transaction ordering help preserve the overall health of the network.
Scale Type	Interval
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Estimate the proportion of honest computational power based on the participation of valid miners. 2) Measure the average time between transaction submission and confirmation. 3) Compute the variability of the minimum transaction fees required for block inclusion over time. 4) Normalize the obtained values. 5) Combine the factors into a single index according to the weights defined by the evaluation model.
References	1) BitcoinF: Achieving Fairness for Bitcoin in Transaction-Fee-Only Model

Tabela 41: Metrics Catalog: Blockchain Size

Metric	Blockchain Size
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Measures the total volume of data stored in the blockchain, including blocks, transactions, headers, and meta-data. This metric represents the accumulated size of the ledger over time and indicates the storage effort required to keep a full node synchronized with the network.
Objective	To assess the impact of blockchain growth on scalability and decentralization. A large blockchain size may hinder ordinary users from running full nodes, increasing reliance on centralized services for data storage, querying, and verification.
Equation	$S_{bc}(t) = \sum size(B_i),$ where $size(B_i)$ is the size of block i , and the sum includes all blocks up to time t . The growth rate can be expressed as $\Delta S_{bc}/\Delta t$.
Comment	Blockchain size directly affects the sustainability of the system. As the ledger grows, storage costs, node synchronization time, and maintenance complexity increase. This may reduce the number of independent nodes and favor centralized data access solutions.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select a fully synchronized full node. 2) Obtain the size of all locally stored blocks. 3) Sum the block sizes to compute the total blockchain size. 4) Repeat the measurement at different times to observe growth. 5) Compare results across different blockchain networks if needed.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 42: Metrics Catalog: Clean Data Rate

Metric	Clean Data Rate
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Measures the proportion of attributes or records that remain valid, complete, and consistent after the data verification and cleaning process in a blockchain system. This metric indicates the quality level of the data made available for analysis, sharing, or trading on the network.
Objective	To evaluate the effectiveness of data cleaning and validation mechanisms applied before storage or exchange in a blockchain. The metric aims to ensure that the data used exhibits high quality by reducing noise, missing values, semantic inconsistencies, and incorrect data types.
Equation	<p>Clean Data Rate = N_{valid}/N_{total}, where N_{valid} is the number of valid attributes or records after cleaning, and N_{total} is the total analyzed.</p> <p>Alternatively, a weighted index can be used: $EUID_{i2} = \lambda_1(1 - V'_{1j}) + \lambda_2(1 - V'_{2j}) + \lambda_3(1 - V'_{3j})$, where V'_{1j}, V'_{2j}, and V'_{3j} represent null values, anomalous values, and incorrect data types, respectively, and λ_k denotes the weight of each factor.</p>
Comment	The clean data rate directly reflects the practical usability of a dataset in blockchain environments. High values indicate that validation and cleaning processes are effective, increasing the reliability of analytics and the economic value of traded data. Low values reveal significant noise, reducing dataset quality and consumer trust.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select the dataset submitted to the blockchain system. 2) Apply checks for null values, anomalies, and incorrect data types. 3) Correct or discard invalid records according to predefined rules. 4) Count the number of valid attributes or records after cleaning. 5) Compute the clean data rate or the weighted index using the defined equation.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Trading System for Big Data

Tabela 43: Metrics Catalog: Confirmed Block Rate

Metric	Confirmed Block Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Measures the proportion of proposed blocks that are effectively confirmed and added to the main blockchain. This metric indicates how often the consensus process validates blocks without them being discarded, replaced, or becoming orphaned.
Objective	To evaluate the stability and reliability of the consensus mechanism in distributed blockchain networks. A high confirmed block rate indicates good synchronization among nodes, while low values suggest propagation issues, excessive latency, or coordination failures among validators.
Equation	Confirmed Block Rate = $N_{confirmed}/N_{proposed}$, where $N_{confirmed}$ is the number of blocks validated and included in the main chain, and $N_{proposed}$ is the total number of blocks proposed during the same period.
Comment	This metric directly reflects the operational efficiency of consensus. High values indicate that most proposed blocks contribute to the effective growth of the blockchain, reducing resource waste. Low values reveal a higher occurrence of forks, orphan blocks, or propagation delays, which compromise network reliability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define an observation window. 2) Count all blocks proposed by validators. 3) Identify which blocks were confirmed and included in the main chain. 4) Compute the ratio between confirmed and proposed blocks. 5) Compare the results under different load levels and network conditions.
References	1) A Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture Based on a Secure OpenFlow Protocol Controller Channel

Tabela 44: Metrics Catalog: Communication Complexity

Metric	Communication Complexity
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behaviour
Definition	Measures the number of messages exchanged among nodes in a blockchain network during distributed operations such as consensus, state synchronization, or shard allocation. This metric expresses the communication cost required for nodes to maintain a consistent view of the system.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency and scalability of inter-node communication in blockchain protocols. In sharded systems, communication complexity directly affects latency, bandwidth consumption, and the network's ability to scale.
Equation	$CC = f(n, f)$, where n is the total number of participating nodes and f is the number of faulty or Byzantine nodes. Depending on the protocol, communication complexity may grow as $O(n)$, $O(n^2)$, or $O(n^3)$.
Comment	Communication complexity indicates how much messaging the network requires to operate correctly. Protocols with lower growth in message exchanges tend to scale better and exhibit lower delays, while protocols with high complexity generate significant network overhead and may become impractical in large-scale distributed systems.
Scale Type	Ordinal
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select the blockchain or sharding protocol to be evaluated. 2) Define the number of participating nodes in the network. 3) Record the total number of messages exchanged during operations such as node joining, consensus, and shard reallocation. 4) Estimate how communication grows as a function of n. 5) Compare the observed complexity across different protocols.
References	1) Analysing and Improving Shard Allocation Protocols for Sharded Blockchains

Tabela 45: Metrics Catalog: Computational Cost

Metric	Computational Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of processing resources required to execute a task or a set of operations in a blockchain-based system, typically measured as the average execution time per task.
Objective	To evaluate the processing efficiency of the system when executing operations such as authentication, data sharing, and smart contract execution, enabling comparisons between approaches and the identification of optimization gains.
Equation	Computational Cost = average execution time of the evaluated tasks over a given experiment or period.
Comment	Lower values indicate higher computational efficiency. This metric reflects the aggregated processing cost, including cryptographic operations and contract logic, and should only be compared across scenarios using the same hardware, dataset, and configuration parameters.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the type of task or operation to be evaluated. 2) Instrument the system to record start and end times for each execution. 3) Run tests under different data sizes or configurations. 4) Compute the average execution time and percentiles (p95). 5) Compare the results with alternative approaches under the same conditions.
References	1) Optimization with Blockchain-based Secure Authentication and Collaborative Data Sharing Model in Cloud

Tabela 46: Metrics Catalog: Consensus Success Rate

Metric	Consensus Success Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Probability that the consensus process in a blockchain network reaches a valid agreement among participating nodes. It represents the proportion of consensus rounds that complete successfully, even in the presence of communication failures, packet losses, or temporary node unavailability.
Objective	To evaluate the robustness and reliability of consensus mechanisms, especially in non-ideal communication environments such as wireless, IoT, IIoT, and 6G networks, where interference, noise, and distance affect message exchange between nodes.
Equation	Consensus Success Rate = number of successful consensus rounds / total number of rounds. In multi-phase protocols (e.g., PBFT), the success rate can be modeled as: $P_c = P_{\text{pre-prepare}} \times P_{\text{prepare}} \times P_{\text{commit}} \times P_{\text{reply}}$.
Comment	In wireless environments, the consensus success rate is strongly influenced by communication channel quality. Interference, signal attenuation, and greater distance between nodes reduce the probability of correct message exchange, increasing the likelihood of consensus failures. More stable communication technologies tend to improve this rate.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the consensus protocol used (e.g., PBFT or RAFT) and the number of participating nodes. 2) Execute multiple consensus rounds under controlled or simulated conditions. 3) Record, for each round, whether consensus was successfully achieved. 4) Compute the proportion of successful rounds relative to the total. 5) Repeat the measurement while varying network conditions (interference, distance, signal threshold) to analyze sensitivity.
References	1) Performance Analysis and Comparison of Nonideal Wireless PBFT and RAFT Consensus Networks in 6G Communications

Tabela 47: Metrics Catalog: Consensus Time

Attribute Name (Title)	Consensus Time
ISO/IEC Characteristic	25010 Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behaviour
Definition	Time required for the participating nodes of a blockchain consensus mechanism to reach a valid agreement on the ordering and confirmation of transactions. It represents the interval between the submission of a proposal and the final commit in the ledger.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal performance of consensus mechanisms, especially in permissioned networks, supporting decisions about endorsement policies, node configuration, and blockchain service planning with a balance between performance, reliability, and operational cost.
Equation	<p>The consensus time can be estimated as the sum of the main stages of the process:</p> $T_c = T_{\text{req}} + T_{\text{endorsement}} + T_{\text{ordering}} + T_{\text{commit}}$ <p>where T_{req} is the request submission time, $T_{\text{endorsement}}$ is the time for endorsement by the nodes required by the policy, T_{ordering} is the block ordering time, and T_{commit} is the validation and ledger writing time.</p>
Comment	Stricter endorsement policies increase consensus time because more nodes must participate before confirmation. More flexible policies reduce the time but may decrease fault tolerance. Service configurations, such as the number of nodes and fault rate, directly influence this metric.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the consensus mechanism and the blockchain platform used. 2) Configure endorsement or quorum policies (e.g., AND, OR, K-out-of-N). 3) Submit transactions and record the proposal submission time. 4) Record the final commit time in the ledger. 5) Compute the consensus time and report statistics such as mean and percentiles (p50, p95, p99).
References	1) A model-based approach for planning blockchain service provisioning

Tabela 48: Metrics Catalog: CPU Overhead

Attribute Name (Title)	CPU Overhead
ISO/IEC Characteristic	25010 Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Additional CPU processing required by a blockchain node to execute functions such as transaction validation, policy enforcement, consensus execution, and ledger updates, compared to an execution without these blockchain functions.
Objective	To evaluate the computational impact of using blockchain on participating nodes, especially in resource-constrained environments such as IoT, supporting design decisions, policy optimization, and the selection of more efficient architectures.
Equation	<p>CPU Overhead (%) =</p> $\frac{T_{\text{with blockchain}} - T_{\text{baseline}}}{T_{\text{baseline}}} \times 100$ <p>or alternatively:</p> $\text{CPU Overhead} = CPU_{\text{with blockchain}} - CPU_{\text{baseline}}$
Comment	The higher the complexity of policies and consensus processing, the higher the CPU overhead tends to be. Efficient policy interpretation and dynamic conflict resolution strategies can significantly reduce this impact, making blockchain more viable for devices with limited computational capacity.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the evaluation scenario and the blockchain node to be monitored. 2) Run the system with blockchain mechanisms enabled, applying a controlled transaction load. 3) Monitor the average and peak CPU usage during execution. 4) Run the same scenario without blockchain mechanisms (baseline). 5) Compute the percentage difference to estimate CPU overhead.
References	1) Fast Policy Interpretation and Dynamic Conflict Resolution for Blockchain-Based IoT System

Tabela 49: Metrics Catalog: CPU Usage

Attribute Name (Title)	CPU Usage
ISO/IEC Characteristic	25010 Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Proportion of CPU processing capacity used by a blockchain node during normal operation, including tasks such as block validation, smart contract execution, and inter-node communication.
Objective	To assess the computational load imposed by the blockchain system on participating nodes, verifying whether CPU utilization is compatible with resource-limited infrastructure environments, such as healthcare systems in developing countries.
Equation	$\text{CPU Usage (\%)} = (T_{active} / T_{total}) \times 100,$ <p>where T_{active} is the time during which the CPU was executing blockchain-related processes and T_{total} is the total observation time.</p>
Comment	Moderate CPU usage indicates the system can operate stably without overloading the hardware. Persistently high values suggest risk of performance degradation, increased energy consumption, and the need to optimize the architecture or smart contracts.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain nodes and smart contracts in the test environment. 2) Execute transactions under different load levels. 3) Monitor average and peak CPU usage during execution. 4) Record the observation period and load conditions. 5) Compare results across scenarios or against alternative architectures.
References	1) Blockchain-based Electronic Healthcare Information System Optimized for Developing Countries

Tabela 50: Metrics Catalog: CPU Utilization

Metric	CPU Utilization
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Average percentage of CPU occupancy of blockchain network nodes over an observation period, considering activities such as block validation, smart contract execution, and inter-node communication.
Objective	To evaluate whether the computational load imposed by the blockchain system remains within sustainable limits, avoiding CPU saturation and ensuring service stability and availability in resource-constrained environments.
Equation	$\text{CPU Utilization (\%)} = (\text{CPU active time} / \text{Total observation time}) \times 100.$ <p>Active time includes transaction processing, consensus, and network support operations.</p>
Comment	Moderate values indicate a balance between performance and resource usage. Persistently high utilization suggests risk of saturation and service degradation, while very low values may indicate underutilization of the infrastructure.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Run the blockchain system in a controlled environment. 2) Define the observation period. 3) Continuously monitor CPU utilization on each node. 4) Compute the mean (and, when necessary, percentiles) over time. 5) Compare the results with SLA thresholds or system requirements.
References	1) Blockchain-based Electronic Healthcare Information System Optimized for Developing Countries

Tabela 51: Metrics Catalog: Cumulative Weight

Metric	Cumulative Weight
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Sum of the weights of the transactions that directly or indirectly approve a given transaction in a directed acyclic graph (DAG)-based ledger. Cumulative weight reflects the level of acceptance and trust assigned to the transaction by the network.
Objective	To assess the level of confirmation and security of a transaction in DAG-based blockchain systems, especially in IoT environments where lightweight, fast, and scalable consensus without blocks is required.
Equation	$CW(T_i) = w_i + \sum w_j$, where w_i is the weight of transaction T_i and w_j are the weights of the transactions that directly or indirectly approve T_i .
Comment	Higher cumulative weight values indicate that the transaction has been widely approved by the network and is less susceptible to conflicts or reversals. Lower values usually correspond to recent or weakly confirmed transactions.
Scale Type	Interval
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Represent the set of transactions as a DAG. 2) Assign an individual weight to each transaction. 3) Identify all transactions that directly or indirectly approve the transaction of interest. 4) Sum the weights according to the defined equation. 5) Compare values across transactions or over time to evaluate the confirmation level.
References	1) Direct Acyclic Graph-based Ledger for Internet of Things: Performance and Security Analysis

Tabela 52: Metrics Catalog: Data Access Rate

Metric	Data Access Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Number of data access operations (read or sharing) that a blockchain system can perform per unit of time, considering authentication, encryption, and verification steps.
Objective	To evaluate the capacity of the blockchain system to access and share data efficiently under multiple simultaneous requests, indicating whether performance remains stable in cloud computing environments with large data volumes.
Equation	Data Access Rate = $N_{\text{accesses}}/T_{\text{execution}}$, where N_{accesses} is the number of successfully completed data access operations and $T_{\text{execution}}$ is the total observation time.
Comment	Higher values indicate that the system can serve many access requests in a short time while maintaining efficiency under high demand. Lower values may indicate bottlenecks in authentication, encryption, or network communication.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain system in the cloud environment. 2) Define test scenarios with different numbers of users and request volumes. 3) Execute data read and sharing operations. 4) Record the number of completed accesses and the total execution time. 5) Compute the access rate and compare it with other approaches or configurations.
References	1) Block chain based IAS protocol to enhance security and privacy in cloud computing

Tabela 53: Metrics Catalog: Data Confidentiality

Metric	Data Confidentiality
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Confidentiality
Definition	Degree to which data stored or transmitted in a blockchain system remains inaccessible to unauthorized entities, even in the presence of interception or unauthorized access.
Objective	To evaluate the effectiveness of the security mechanisms employed by the blockchain system to protect sensitive data, ensuring that only authorized participants can read or use the information.
Equation	$\text{Data Confidentiality} = 1 - (N_{\text{unauthorized}}/N_{\text{total attempts}})$, where $N_{\text{unauthorized}}$ represents successful unauthorized accesses during the observation period.
Comment	Higher values indicate stronger protection against data leakage or unauthorized reading. Lower values suggest weaknesses in encryption, authentication, or access control.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain system in the target environment. 2) Enable encryption and authentication mechanisms. 3) Monitor authorized and unauthorized access attempts. 4) Record successful unauthorized accesses. 5) Compute the metric over the observation period.
References	1) Block chain based IAS protocol to enhance security and privacy in cloud computing

Tabela 54: Metrics Catalog: Data Consistency

Metric	Data Consistency
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Degree to which data and states maintained by different nodes or controllers in a blockchain system remain coherent and synchronized over time.
Objective	To evaluate the ability of the blockchain system to maintain consistent information across distributed components, avoiding state divergence that could cause operational failures in distributed control architectures.
Equation	$\text{Data Consistency} = 1 - (N_{\text{divergences}}/N_{\text{states}}),$ <p>where $N_{\text{divergences}}$ is the number of inconsistencies detected among nodes and N_{states} is the total number of monitored states.</p>
Comment	Higher values indicate that the system maintains uniform and reliable states across nodes. Lower values suggest synchronization issues, communication delays, or failures in data replication.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the distributed architecture with multiple nodes or controllers and a blockchain ledger. 2) Define which states or data must remain synchronized. 3) Introduce controlled failures or communication delays. 4) Compare observed states across nodes over time. 5) Compute the metric based on the number of detected divergences.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Distributed Control for Software Defined Optical Networking

Tabela 55: Metrics Catalog: Data Consumption

Metric	Data Consumption
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Measures the amount of data transmitted and stored by a blockchain system during its operation, considering network traffic, transaction sizes, ledger growth, and auxiliary data required for validation and verification.
Objective	To evaluate the impact of data volume on the efficiency and scalability of blockchain systems. In certificate revocation-based solutions, data consumption reflects the cost of keeping revocation information distributed, up to date, and verifiable by all network participants.
Equation	$DC = D_{tx} + D_{ctrl} + D_{ledger}$, where D_{tx} represents transaction data volume, D_{ctrl} control and signaling data, and D_{ledger} the growth of distributed storage over time.
Comment	The blockchain-based certificate revocation study shows that although data consumption increases compared to centralized solutions, the overhead is compensated by the elimination of single points of failure and increased transparency and availability. Data consumption is strongly associated with the number of revoked certificates and update frequency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the operating scenario (e.g., certificate issuance and revocation). 2) Measure the average size of blockchain transactions. 3) Monitor network traffic generated during block propagation. 4) Evaluate ledger growth over time. 5) Compute total data consumption (DC). 6) Compare results with traditional approaches (e.g., CRL and OCSP).
References	Khan, M. A.; Salah, K. A Blockchain-Based Certificate Revocation. IEEE Access, 2018.

Tabela 56: Metrics Catalog: Data Integrity

Metric	Data Integrity
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Degree to which data stored or transmitted by a blockchain system remains correct, complete, and unaltered, allowing any unauthorized modification to be detected.
Objective	To evaluate the ability of the blockchain system to protect data against unauthorized changes, ensuring that records, certificates, or events remain authentic and verifiable over time.
Equation	$\text{Data Integrity} = 1 - (N_{\text{failures}}/N_{\text{verifications}}),$ where N_{failures} is the number of failed integrity checks and $N_{\text{verifications}}$ is the total number of checks performed.
Comment	Values close to 1 indicate that data remains intact and reliable. Lower values suggest verification failures, record corruption, or weaknesses in cryptographic mechanisms.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain system in the application environment. 2) Record data, certificates, or events on the blockchain. 3) Compute hashes and digital signatures for each record. 4) Periodically verify whether stored data matches the original values. 5) Count verification failures and compute the metric.
References	1) Securing Data Exchange in the Convergence of Metaverse and IoT Applications

Tabela 57: Metrics Catalog: Data Utility Rate

Metric	Data Utility Rate
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Proportion of blockchain-recorded data that remains valid, consistent, and useful when actually consumed by applications that rely on this information.
Objective	To evaluate whether the blockchain's recording, validation, and consensus mechanisms preserve the practical usefulness of data for applications, without compromising its accuracy or informational value.
Equation	$\text{Data Utility Rate} = (\text{amount of valid and consistent data used by the application}) / (\text{total amount of data processed by the application}).$
Comment	Higher values indicate that blockchain-recorded data retains its utility and reliability when used by applications. Lower values suggest loss of informational quality, inconsistencies, or negative impacts of validation and confirmation processes on the practical use of data.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify applications that consume data from the blockchain. 2) Verify the consistency and correctness of the data actually used by the application. 3) Count the amount of valid data relative to the total processed. 4) Compute the data utility rate. 5) Compare the results with equivalent data processed outside the blockchain, when applicable.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Trading System for Big Data

Tabela 58: Metrics Catalog: Decentralization Level

Metric	Decentralization Level
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Degree to which control, validation, and maintenance of the blockchain are distributed among multiple independent participants, without reliance on a single central authority.
Objective	To assess the distribution of power within the blockchain network, indicating how resistant the system is to censorship, data manipulation, collusion among participants, or control attacks.
Equation	Decentralization Level = $1 - \sum p_i^2$, where p_i is the proportion of consensus power held by participant i . Values close to 1 indicate high decentralization, while values close to 0 indicate centralization.
Comment	Higher values indicate that validation power is well distributed among multiple participants, increasing system security and integrity. Lower values indicate power concentration, which may facilitate manipulation, censorship, or coordinated attacks.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify all participants involved in blockchain consensus. 2) Determine the share of consensus power of each participant (hashrate, stake, or authority). 3) Compute the sum of the squares of these proportions. 4) Subtract the result from 1 to obtain the decentralization level. 5) Compare the resulting value with reference thresholds to classify the network.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof

Tabela 59: Metrics Catalog: Deployment Cost

Metric	Deployment Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Total cost required to deploy smart contracts and initialize a blockchain system on a given network, considering gas consumption and the gas price paid at the time of deployment.
Objective	To evaluate the initial economic feasibility of a blockchain solution, allowing contracts and platforms to be compared in terms of deployment cost before operations begin.
Equation	Deployment Cost = $GasUsed_{\text{deploy}} \times GasPrice$, where $GasUsed_{\text{deploy}}$ is the total gas consumed during contract deployment.
Comment	Lower values indicate lighter contracts and better suitability for large-scale deployments. High values are usually associated with complex contracts, large bytecode, or intensive storage usage.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prepare the smart contract for deployment. 2) Deploy the contract on the chosen network (testnet or mainnet). 3) Record the total gas consumed from the transaction receipt. 4) Multiply the gas consumed by the current gas price. 5) Repeat the measurement under different scenarios to obtain average values.
References	1) MRBSChain: a novel scalable medical records binance smart chain framework enabling a paradigm shift in medical records management

Tabela 60: Metrics Catalog: Download Time

Metric	Download Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Total time required to retrieve and transfer a file stored in a blockchain-based storage platform, from the moment the request is sent until the client completes the download.
Objective	To evaluate the performance and responsiveness of decentralized storage platforms during file read operations, enabling comparison with traditional cloud storage services.
Equation	Download Time = $t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{start}}$, where t_{start} is the moment when the download request is issued and t_{end} is the moment when the file is fully received.
Comment	Shorter times indicate higher data retrieval efficiency. High values may indicate bandwidth limitations, low node availability, or inadequate redundancy and parallelism configuration.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain-based storage platform. 2) Select files of different sizes for testing. 3) Perform multiple download operations. 4) Record the total time of each download. 5) Compute averages and compare results across platforms.
References	1) Performance and Cost Analysis of Sia, a Blockchain-Based Storage Platform

Tabela 61: Metrics Catalog: Dynamic Arrival Rate

Metric	Dynamic Arrival Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Frequency at which new transactions arrive at the ordering service of a blockchain network over time, expressed in transactions per second. This rate can vary dynamically according to user and application behavior.
Objective	To evaluate whether the volume of transactions submitted to the network remains within the processing capacity of the ordering service, helping to identify overload situations and the need for infrastructure scaling.
Equation	$P = \lambda/\mu$, where λ is the transaction arrival rate (transactions per second) and μ is the service rate of the ordering node. The system remains stable while $P < 1$.
Comment	When the arrival rate approaches or exceeds the service capacity of the ordering node, queues begin to build up and processing time increases. Keeping λ below μ is essential to ensure network stability and good performance.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain network with an active ordering service. 2) Define the service rate of the ordering node. 3) Generate transaction workloads with varying arrival rates. 4) Measure the actual arrival rate at the ordering service. 5) Compute the utilization factor P and identify saturation points.
References	1) Performance Evaluation of M/D/1 Queuing Model on Hyperledger Fabric

Tabela 62: Metrics Catalog: Elapsed Time

Metric	Elapsed Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Total time required for a smart contract to be executed on a blockchain network, measured from transaction submission to the final confirmation of the result on the network. This time includes network communication, consensus, and contract execution.
Objective	To evaluate the speed and responsiveness of smart contract execution across different blockchain networks, enabling comparison of the impact of consensus, infrastructure, and computational complexity on system response time.
Equation	$ET = t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{start}}$, where t_{start} is the moment when the transaction is submitted and t_{end} is the moment when contract execution is finally confirmed on the blockchain.
Comment	Elapsed time tends to increase with contract complexity and with the need to write state to the blockchain. In many cases, the delay is not in computation itself but in consensus and transaction propagation across the network.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Implement smart contracts representative of the application. 2) Deploy the contracts on different blockchain networks. 3) Execute the contracts under varying loads and complexities. 4) Record the transaction submission time and the final confirmation time. 5) Compute the average elapsed time and compare it across the evaluated networks.
References	1) Performance Analysis of Blockchain Networks through Smart Contracts

Tabela 63: Metrics Catalog: Empty Block Rate

Metric	Empty Block Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Proportion of blocks produced in the blockchain that do not contain user transactions, including only structural block information and, when applicable, the reward transaction.
Objective	To evaluate how effectively the blockchain's capacity to process transactions is being used. A high empty block rate indicates wasted network resources and potential inefficiency in transaction inclusion.
Equation	Empty Block Rate = (number of blocks without user transactions) / (total number of analyzed blocks).
Comment	Low values indicate good use of block space and higher network efficiency. High values suggest issues such as propagation delays, opportunistic validator strategies, or conservative inclusion policies, which reduce effective throughput and may increase the confirmation time perceived by users.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain network and the block range or time window to be analyzed. 2) Collect the blocks produced during the period, including the number of transactions in each block. 3) Classify as empty those blocks that contain no user transactions. 4) Compute the ratio between empty blocks and the total number of observed blocks. 5) Analyze how the rate varies over time and under different network conditions.
References	1) Impact of Geo-Distribution and Mining Pools on Blockchains: A Study of Ethereum

Tabela 64: Metrics Catalog: Event Omission Rate

Metric	Event Omission Rate
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Proportion of events that are expected to be recorded or observed on the blockchain but do not appear in the analyzed records.
Objective	To evaluate whether all relevant events expected by an application or process are actually recorded and made available, indicating the level of functional completeness and data transparency.
Equation	Event Omission Rate = $1 - \frac{\text{number of observed events}}{\text{number of expected events}}$.
Comment	Low values indicate that most expected events are present, suggesting good completeness and record reliability. High values indicate collection failures, delays, excessive reliance on intermediaries, or systematic omissions, reducing transparency and auditability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Clearly define which events are expected based on smart contracts, system rules, or reference records. 2) Collect the events actually observed on the blockchain or through indexing services. 3) Compute the ratio between observed and expected events. 4) Apply the metric equation to obtain the omission rate. 5) Compare different data sources (direct on-chain vs indexers) to identify possible causes of omissions.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 65: Metrics Catalog: Execution Cost

Metric	Execution Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Total cost associated with executing a transaction or smart contract, considering computational effort, inter-node communication, and, when applicable, the monetary cost charged by the network.
Objective	To evaluate the economic and operational efficiency of blockchain executions, enabling comparison across architectures, platforms, and configurations, and assessing the feasibility of cost-sensitive applications.
Equation	<p>Execution Cost = Computational Cost + Communication Cost + Storage Cost.</p> <p>In gas-based blockchains, it can be expressed as: $Execution\ Cost = GasUsed \times GasPrice$.</p>
Comment	Lower values indicate more efficient executions. In permissioned networks, execution cost tends to be lower because explicit gas fees are not required. In public networks, high costs may limit application usage, requiring optimizations or hybrid architectures.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the operation to be evaluated (e.g., data submission, update, or query). 2) Execute the operation in a controlled environment or test network. 3) Collect processing, communication, and storage information from logs or monitoring tools. 4) Compute the total execution cost using the defined equation. 5) Compare results across different platforms or network configurations.
References	1) MedHypChain: A Patient-Centered Interoperability Hyperledger-Based Medical Healthcare System Regulation in COVID-19 Pandemic

Tabela 66: Metrics Catalog: Failed Request Rate

Metric	Failed Request Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of requests or transactions that are not successfully completed relative to the total number of requests submitted to the blockchain system.
Objective	To evaluate the operational reliability of the blockchain system by verifying its ability to handle high loads and maintain correct execution of requests and transactions.
Equation	Failed Request Rate = (number of failed requests / total number of requests) \times 100%.
Comment	Lower values indicate higher system reliability and robustness. High rates suggest problems such as overload, communication failures, timeouts, or consensus instability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the type of request being evaluated (query or transaction). 2) Run the system under different load levels. 3) Record the total number of submitted requests. 4) Record the number of failed requests. 5) Compute the failed request rate and analyze how it varies with load.
References	1) T-DSES: A Blockchain-powered Trusted Decentralized Service Eco-System

Tabela 67: Metrics Catalog: Failure Recovery Rate

Metric	Failure Recovery Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Recoverability
Definition	Proportion of failures detected in a blockchain system that are successfully recovered, allowing the service to return to normal operation after problems in nodes, validators, or control components.
Objective	To evaluate the system's ability to automatically recover from failures, indicating the effectiveness of fault-tolerance and service restoration mechanisms in blockchain and distributed system architectures.
Equation	Failure Recovery Rate = (number of recovered failures) / (total number of detected failures).
Comment	Higher values indicate stronger recovery capability and system resilience. Lower values suggest that failures persist longer, increasing downtime and operational risk.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the types of failures to be monitored (node crash, validator failure, connectivity loss). 2) Automatically log each detected failure. 3) Monitor the recovery mechanisms triggered by the system. 4) Verify whether the service was correctly restored after each failure. 5) Count the total number of failures and the number of recovered failures. 6) Compute the failure recovery rate for the analyzed period.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Distributed Control for Software Defined Optical Networking

Tabela 68: Metrics Catalog: Fault Tolerance Level

Metric	Fault Tolerance Level
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Ability of the blockchain system to continue operating correctly even when part of its components fail, such as nodes, validators, or controllers.
Objective	To evaluate the robustness of the blockchain architecture in the presence of failures, indicating how well the system maintains consensus, transaction execution, and data integrity under adverse conditions.
Equation	$\text{Fault Tolerance Level} = \frac{\text{(number of tolerated failures)}}{\text{(maximum acceptable number of failures)}}$
Comment	Higher values indicate stronger system resilience, allowing correct operation even with partial failures. Lower values suggest architectural vulnerability or excessive dependence on critical components.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the system architecture and consensus mechanism. 2) Identify the maximum number of acceptable failures according to the theoretical model or system design. 3) Introduce controlled failures in nodes or controllers. 4) Verify how many failures the system can tolerate while still operating correctly. 5) Compute the ratio between tolerated and maximum acceptable failures.
References	1) Blockchain-based Secure Distributed Control for Software Defined Optical Networking

Tabela 69: Metrics Catalog: Forgery Resistance Level

Metric	Forgery Resistance Level
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Ability of the blockchain system to prevent the creation or acceptance of forged data, such as signatures, bids, or cryptographic proofs, without knowledge of the legitimate keys or secrets.
Objective	To evaluate how secure the system is against forgery attempts, ensuring that only authentic and valid data is accepted and recorded, thereby preserving process integrity and trustworthiness.
Equation	Forgery Resistance Level = $1 - \frac{\text{number of detected forgeries}}{\text{total number of forgery attempts}}$.
Comment	Values close to 1 indicate high resistance, meaning that almost all forgery attempts are rejected. Lower values suggest weaknesses in cryptographic implementation or verification mechanisms.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the artifacts to be protected (signatures, bids, cryptographic proofs). 2) Implement verification mechanisms in the smart contract. 3) Perform tests with forgery attempts without access to legitimate secrets. 4) Record the total number of attempts and how many were correctly rejected. 5) Compute the metric based on the proportion of detected forgeries.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof

Tabela 70: Metrics Catalog: Fork Frequency

Metric	Fork Frequency
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Frequency at which forks occur in the blockchain, that is, situations in which two or more blocks are created almost simultaneously for the same chain position, generating temporary branches until one is selected as the main chain.
Objective	To evaluate the stability of consensus and the efficiency of block propagation in the network. A high fork frequency indicates wasted work, increased confirmation time, and reduced system reliability.
Equation	Fork Frequency = (number of forks) / (total number of observed blocks), or Fork Frequency = (number of forks) / (observation time).
Comment	Lower values indicate a stable network with good block propagation and efficient consensus. High values suggest network delays, large blocks, consensus difficulty, or adversarial behavior, increasing the risk of chain reorganizations.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network and the observation window. 2) Monitor block creation and identify competing blocks at the same height. 3) Count the number of forks occurring during the period. 4) Compute the frequency relative to the number of blocks or the observation time. 5) Analyze the relationship between this metric and propagation latency and confirmation time.
References	1) A Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture Based on a Secure OpenFlow Protocol Controller Channel

Tabela 71: Metrics Catalog: Gas Fee

Metric	Gas Fee
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount paid for a transaction or smart contract to be processed and included in the blockchain. The gas fee is obtained by multiplying the amount of gas consumed by the operation by the gas price defined by the network, reflecting computational cost and network congestion at execution time.
Objective	To evaluate the financial cost of operations in a blockchain network, supporting smart contract optimization, network selection, and the use of off-chain strategies in applications with high transaction volumes, such as e-health and IoT.
Equation	Gas Fee = $gasUsed \times gasPrice$. Fiat cost = Gas Fee \times cryptocurrency exchange rate.
Comment	Higher gas fees indicate higher transaction execution costs, usually associated with congested networks or inefficient contracts. Lower fees reduce financial cost but may increase confirmation time if the transaction is not prioritized by validators.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	1) Define the blockchain network and the analysis period. 2) Collect $gasUsed$ and $gasPrice$ values for each transaction. 3) Compute individual gas fees and their average over the period. 4) Convert the value to fiat currency if needed. 5) Analyze how the fee varies with network congestion.
References	1) Distributed Network Slicing Management Using Blockchains in E-Health Environments

Tabela 72: Metrics Catalog: Gas-Time Ratio

Metric	Gas-Time Ratio
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Relationship between the amount of gas consumed and the total time required to execute and confirm a transaction or smart contract. This metric expresses how much computational resource (gas) is spent per unit of time during execution.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal efficiency of gas usage by relating computational consumption to transaction processing and confirmation time. The metric helps identify contracts or operations that consume large amounts of gas relative to their execution time.
Equation	$Gas\text{-}to\text{-}Time\ Ratio = GasUsed / ExecutionTime.$
Comment	Lower values indicate that gas consumption is efficiently distributed over execution time. Higher values may indicate costly operations, confirmation delays, or processing bottlenecks, suggesting the need for contract or infrastructure optimization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Record the transaction submission time (t_{start}). 2) Record the transaction confirmation time (t_{end}). 3) Compute execution time as $t_{end} - t_{start}$. 4) Collect the <i>gasUsed</i> value from the transaction receipt. 5) Compute the ratio between gas consumption and execution time.
References	1) Empirically Analyzing Ethereum's Gas Mechanism

Tabela 73: Metrics Catalog: Genuine User Detection Rate

Metric	Genuine User Detection Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Authenticity
Definition	Proportion of legitimate users correctly recognized by the authentication system relative to the total number of access attempts. This metric indicates how well the mechanism identifies genuine users without confusing them with malicious entities.
Objective	To evaluate the effectiveness of the blockchain-based authentication mechanism in recognizing legitimate users, ensuring secure and reliable access to data stored in decentralized systems.
Equation	Genuine User Detection Rate = (number of correct authentications of legitimate users) / (total number of authentication attempts).
Comment	Higher values indicate that most legitimate users are correctly recognized, reducing unjustified access denials. Lower values suggest failures in the authentication process, which may affect usability and trust in the system.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Implement the blockchain-based access control mechanism. 2) Perform authentication attempts with legitimate users and unauthorized users. 3) Record how many legitimate user attempts are correctly accepted. 4) Count the total number of authentication attempts. 5) Compute the ratio between correct legitimate user authentications and total attempts.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Access Control and Data Sharing Mechanism in Cloud Decentralized Storage System

Tabela 74: Metrics Catalog: Group Conflict Rate

Metric	Group Conflict Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of transactions in a block that depend on each other, forming a large group that cannot be executed in parallel. This metric indicates how tightly coupled the transactions are.
Objective	To evaluate the potential for parallel execution of transactions in blockchain blocks. The lower the group conflict rate, the greater the possibility of executing transactions concurrently and improving performance.
Equation	Group Conflict Rate = (size of the largest group of dependent transactions) / (total number of transactions in the block).
Comment	Low values indicate that few transactions depend on each other, enabling higher parallelism and better performance. High values indicate strong transaction dependencies, requiring more sequential execution and limiting speedup gains.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Represent block transactions as a dependency graph. 2) Identify groups of mutually dependent transactions. 3) Determine the size of the largest identified group. 4) Divide this value by the total number of transactions in the block. 5) Repeat the measurement across multiple blocks and analyze the trend.
References	1) On Exploiting Transaction Concurrency to Speed Up Blockchains

Tabela 75: Metrics Catalog: Insecure Access Modifier Index

Metric	Insecure Access Modifier Index
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of functions in smart contracts that use overly permissive access modifiers, allowing unauthorized users to execute operations that should be restricted. This metric indicates the level of improper exposure of critical functions.
Objective	To evaluate the correctness of access controls implemented in smart contracts by identifying functions that can be exploited by external agents due to inappropriate visibility or permissions.
Equation	Insecure Access Modifier Index = (number of functions with improperly permissive access) / (total number of contract functions).
Comment	Higher values indicate a greater security risk, as sensitive functions become accessible to any user. Lower values indicate that the contract correctly enforces access levels, reducing the likelihood of misuse or attacks.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Analyze the smart contract source code. 2) Identify all functions and their access modifiers. 3) Verify whether the access level of each function is appropriate for its purpose. 4) Count the functions with overly permissive modifiers. 5) Compute the ratio between insecure functions and the total number of functions.
References	1) An efficient distributed and secure algorithm for transaction confirmation in IOTA using cloud computing

Tabela 76: Metrics Catalog: Integer Overflow/Underflow Rate

Metric	Integer Overflow/Underflow Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of arithmetic errors caused by overflow or underflow in numerical operations executed by smart contracts or blockchain system components.
Objective	To evaluate the robustness of the system against arithmetic failures that can produce incorrect results, state corruption, or exploitable vulnerabilities, thereby compromising transaction integrity.
Equation	Integer Overflow/Underflow Rate = (number of overflow or underflow errors) / (total number of evaluated arithmetic operations).
Comment	Lower values indicate strong arithmetic integrity and proper use of boundary checks. Higher values suggest implementation weaknesses and risk of exploitation or critical system failures.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify smart contracts or modules that perform arithmetic operations. 2) Apply static and dynamic analysis to detect overflow and underflow errors. 3) Count the number of detected occurrences. 4) Estimate the total number of evaluated arithmetic operations. 5) Compute the rate and compare across versions or implementations.
References	1) An Efficient Distributed and Secure Algorithm for Transaction Confirmation in IOTA Using Cloud Computing

Tabela 77: Metrics Catalog: Internal Service Centralization Level

Metric	Internal Service Centralization Level
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Degree to which a blockchain or decentralized application depends on internally controlled services operated by a single entity, such as RPC providers, oracles, indexers, or centralized authentication mechanisms.
Objective	To assess structural centralization risks in systems that claim to be decentralized, by identifying internal dependencies that may introduce censorship, service outages, or loss of operational integrity.
Equation	Internal Service Centralization Level = (number of centralized internal services) / (total number of internal services used).
Comment	Higher values indicate strong dependence on a few providers or entities, increasing the risk of single points of failure and censorship. Lower values indicate more distributed internal services and greater system resilience.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify all internal services used by the blockchain or application. 2) Classify each service as centralized or distributed. 3) Count the number of centralized services. 4) Divide by the total number of identified internal services. 5) Analyze the impact of these dependencies on system operation and security.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 78: Metrics Catalog: Number of Invalid Blocks

Metric	Number of Invalid Blocks
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Number of blocks produced in the network that are not included in the main blockchain. These blocks may arise due to propagation delays, forks, or dishonest strategies such as selfish mining, and represent wasted computational effort.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency and reliability of blockchain consensus by identifying resource waste and potential signs of dishonest behavior or communication problems in the network.
Equation	Invalid Block Rate = (number of invalid blocks) / (total number of produced blocks). The absolute value can also be directly analyzed as the total number of invalid blocks observed in the period.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater resource waste and possible consensus problems, such as propagation delays or strategic attacks. Lower values indicate good network synchronization and mostly honest participant behavior.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain observation window. 2) Collect all blocks produced during the period. 3) Identify which blocks were not included in the main chain. 4) Count the total number of invalid blocks. 5) Compute the invalid block rate relative to total produced blocks. 6) Compare results under different network conditions or mining strategies.
References	1) Assessing Blockchain Selfish Mining in an Imperfect Network: Honest and Selfish Miner Views

Tabela 79: Metrics Catalog: Limited Liquidity

Metric	Limited Liquidity
Characteristic	Portability
Subcharacteristic	Adaptability
Definition	Degree of restriction in the movement and conversion of digital assets in a blockchain, caused by low market depth, liquidity concentration, or dependence on intermediaries such as exchanges and bridges. It reflects the difficulty of executing large-volume transactions without significant price impact or without relying on centralized infrastructure.
Objective	To evaluate the economic efficiency and adaptability of the blockchain ecosystem regarding asset transfer and conversion. This metric identifies risks of financial centralization, price manipulation, and operational asset lock-in in environments that claim to be decentralized.
Equation	Limited Liquidity = $1 - (V_{neg}/V_{dem})$, where V_{neg} is the volume that can be traded without exceeding a maximum acceptable price variation (ΔP_{max}) and V_{dem} is the total demanded volume. Higher values indicate lower liquidity.
Comment	Limited liquidity indicates dependence on a small number of providers and higher economic risk. In low-liquidity ecosystems, large transactions tend to cause abrupt price changes or require centralized intermediaries, reducing practical adaptability and decentralization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select the main assets and trading pairs of the ecosystem. 2) Collect order book and traded volume data (on-chain and off-chain). 3) Define a maximum acceptable price variation threshold (ΔP_{max}). 4) Compute the tradable volume within this threshold (V_{neg}). 5) Identify the total demanded volume (V_{dem}). 6) Compute the Limited Liquidity metric and track its variation over time.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 80: Metrics Catalog: Load Reduction

Metric	Load Reduction
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Degree of reduction in computational, communication, or storage load in a blockchain system after the application of optimization mechanisms such as data analytics, filtering, compression, or task delegation to external components. It indicates how much the system can operate with less processing and data transmission effort while maintaining correct functionality.
Objective	To evaluate how efficiently the system reduces the use of computational and network resources, especially in resource-constrained environments such as Internet of Things (IoT) applications. This metric verifies whether optimization strategies effectively relieve system overload without degrading performance.
Equation	Load Reduction = $(L_{orig} - L_{opt})/L_{orig}$, where L_{orig} is the load measured before optimization and L_{opt} is the load measured after applying the reduction mechanism. Higher values indicate greater load reduction.
Comment	Load reduction reflects the direct impact of optimization techniques on system resource consumption. In blockchain-based IoT solutions, reducing the volume of processed and transmitted data lowers node effort, improves scalability, and contributes to lower latency and energy consumption.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Measure the total system load before optimization (L_{orig}), considering processing, communication, or storage. 2) Apply the proposed optimization mechanism, such as data analytics, filtering, compression, or offloading. 3) Measure the total system load again after optimization (L_{opt}). 4) Compute Load Reduction using the defined equation. 5) Repeat the procedure under different data volumes or usage scenarios for comparison.
References	1) A Data Analytics Scheme for Security-Aware and Efficient Data Management in Blockchain-Based IoT Systems

Tabela 81: Metrics Catalog: Maximum Number of Transactions

Metric	Maximum Number of Transactions
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Maximum number of transactions that a blockchain system can process per second under controlled conditions before reaching its capacity limit. It represents the point at which the system starts to saturate and can no longer maintain correct transaction processing.
Objective	To evaluate the maximum processing capacity of the blockchain and determine whether the infrastructure is suitable for high-transaction-volume applications, such as advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) and industrial systems.
Equation	$T_{max} = N_{tx}/t_{total}$, where N_{tx} is the total number of successfully processed transactions and t_{total} is the total experiment time in seconds.
Comment	The maximum number of transactions represents the upper capacity bound of the blockchain. Higher values indicate greater potential scalability. Lower results point to bottlenecks in consensus, node communication, or hardware, which may limit system use in high-demand scenarios.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain environment with defined hardware, network, and consensus parameters. 2) Submit increasing transaction volumes to the system. 3) Identify the point at which the system reaches saturation or significant performance degradation. 4) Record the number of successfully processed transactions and the total test time. 5) Compute the maximum number of transactions per second using the defined equation.
References	1) Blockchain-based AMI framework for data security and privacy protection

Tabela 82: Metrics Catalog: Memory Consumption

Metric	Memory Consumption
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of RAM memory used by a blockchain system during its operation, including transaction processing, smart contract execution, and maintenance of temporary data.
Objective	To evaluate memory usage efficiency in blockchain systems and determine whether the architecture is suitable for resource-constrained environments such as embedded devices or hospital infrastructures.
Equation	Memory Consumption = $\frac{\text{Memory used during execution}}{\text{Memory in initial state}}$ or Relative Consumption (%) = $(\text{Memory used} / \text{Total available memory}) \times 100$.
Comment	Lower memory consumption indicates more efficient resource usage and greater scalability potential. High values may signal inefficient data structures, excessive caching, or excessive reliance on in-memory storage.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain system in a controlled environment. 2) Record memory usage in the system's initial state. 3) Execute typical operations (transactions, validation, and contracts). 4) Monitor average and peak memory consumption during execution. 5) Compute absolute or relative memory consumption according to the defined equation.
References	1) MedHypChain: A Patient-Centered Interoperability Hyperledger-Based Medical Healthcare System Regulation in COVID-19 Pandemic

Tabela 83: Metrics Catalog: Message Delivery Rate

Metric	Message Delivery Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Proportion of messages that are successfully delivered relative to the total number of messages sent between participants in a blockchain network. This metric indicates the reliability of end-to-end communication in the distributed system.
Objective	To evaluate communication reliability in blockchain systems integrated with cloud computing environments by identifying message losses caused by node failures, authentication problems, or network congestion.
Equation	Message Delivery Rate = (number of successfully delivered messages) / (total number of sent messages).
Comment	Higher values indicate stable and reliable communication. Lower values may signal authentication failures, packet loss, faulty nodes, or network congestion.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain system and communication protocol in a cloud environment. 2) Send messages between users and data providers under different load and failure conditions. 3) Record the total number of sent messages. 4) Record the number of messages correctly received at the destination. 5) Compute the ratio between delivered and sent messages.
References	1) Block chain based IAS protocol to enhance security and privacy in cloud computing

Tabela 84: Metrics Catalog: Message Propagation

Metric	Message Propagation
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for a message, such as a transaction or a block, to be received by the majority or all nodes in a peer-to-peer blockchain network.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of communication between blockchain nodes and identify delays that may affect synchronization, block confirmation, and consensus stability.
Equation	<p>Average propagation delay:</p> $D_p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (t_{recv,i} - t_{send})$ <p>Total propagation time:</p> $T_{prop} = \max(t_{recv,i}) - t_{send}$
Comment	Lower values indicate faster information dissemination, leading to more stable consensus and lower risk of forks. Higher values indicate communication bottlenecks, regional connectivity differences, or inefficient network topologies.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select a blockchain network and a set of participating nodes. 2) Record the message sending time (t_{send}) at the source node. 3) Record the reception time ($t_{recv,i}$) at each monitored node. 4) Compute the average delay and total propagation time. 5) Repeat the measurements across different periods and regions to capture network variability.
References	1) Ethna: Analyzing the Underlying Peer-to-Peer Network of Ethereum Blockchain

Tabela 85: Metrics Catalog: Mining Power Utilization

Metric	Mining Power Utilization
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Proportion of the total mining computational power that effectively results in blocks accepted into the main blockchain, relative to the total number of blocks mined.
Objective	To evaluate how efficiently the consensus protocol converts computational effort into useful blockchain progress, reducing wasted energy due to forks and discarded blocks.
Equation	$MPU = \frac{B_{main}}{B_{total}}$ <p>where B_{main} is the number of blocks included in the main chain and B_{total} is the total number of mined blocks.</p>
Comment	Higher values indicate better utilization of mining power. Lower values signal computational waste, typically caused by propagation delays, high fork rates, or inefficient consensus protocols.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define a network observation window. 2) Count all blocks mined during the period. 3) Identify which blocks were included in the main chain. 4) Compute the ratio between accepted and mined blocks. 5) Compare results across different network configurations or consensus protocols.
References	1) Bitcoin-NG: A Scalable Blockchain Protocol

Tabela 86: Metrics Catalog: Mutable Metadata

Metric	Mutable Metadata
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Indicates whether the metadata of a smart contract can be modified after deployment on the blockchain. Metadata includes descriptive information such as name, symbol, URI, or identifiers associated with tokens and digital assets.
Objective	To evaluate the risk of manipulation and loss of integrity in smart contracts by checking whether descriptive information can be altered after deployment, potentially misleading users and compromising trust in on-chain assets.
Equation	$MM = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if functions exist that allow metadata to be changed after d} \\ 0, & \text{if metadata is immutable} \end{cases}$
Comment	Mutable metadata allows administrators or developers to change token information after creation. While this may be legitimate in some cases, it also enables fraud, content replacement, or non-transparent changes, reducing user trust.
Scale Type	Nominal
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Analyze the smart contract source code. 2) Identify metadata variables (e.g., name, symbol, URI, baseURI). 3) Check whether administrative functions allow modifying these values after deployment. 4) Assign $MM = 1$ if any metadata is mutable; otherwise $MM = 0$. 5) Record the result for comparison across contracts or ecosystems.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 87: Metrics Catalog: Mutable Parameters

Metric	Mutable Parameters
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Indicates whether critical parameters of a smart contract can be modified after its deployment on the blockchain. These parameters include economic and operational rules such as fees, transaction limits, issuance, or token allocation.
Objective	To evaluate the risk of manipulation and loss of predictability in smart contracts by verifying whether fundamental rules can be changed after deployment, potentially compromising user trust and system integrity.
Equation	$MP = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if functions exist that allow critical parameters to be changed} \\ 0, & \text{if all critical parameters are immutable} \end{cases}$
Comment	Mutable parameters allow administrators or developers to modify economic rules after the contract is already in use. While this can support maintenance, it also introduces the risk of abuse, unexpected rule changes, or concentration of power, reducing transparency and trust.
Scale Type	Nominal
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Analyze the smart contract source code. 2) Identify critical parameters such as fees, limits, or financial rules. 3) Check whether administrative functions allow modifying these parameters after deployment. 4) Assign $MP = 1$ if any critical parameter is mutable; otherwise $MP = 0$. 5) Record the result for comparison across contracts or ecosystems.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 88: Metrics Catalog: Network Bandwidth

Metric	Network Bandwidth
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Average amount of data transmitted per second in a blockchain network during communication among nodes and auxiliary services (e.g., IPFS, IoT devices, or UAVs). This metric indicates how much the network is stressed to support transactions and information exchange.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of network usage in distributed blockchain systems. Lower bandwidth consumption indicates lower network overhead, better operational efficiency, and improved scalability, especially in real-time or data-intensive applications.
Equation	$BW = \frac{D_{total}}{T}$ <p>where D_{total} is the total volume of data transmitted (in bits) and T is the transmission time (in seconds).</p>
Comment	Lower values indicate more efficient communication with reduced network consumption. Higher values suggest network overhead, increased operational cost, and potential scalability limitations. In architectures that combine blockchain with off-chain storage (e.g., IPFS), bandwidth usage tends to be lower.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network observation interval $[t_0, t_1]$. 2) Monitor data traffic among blockchain nodes and external services. 3) Record the total volume of transmitted data during the interval. 4) Measure the total transmission time. 5) Compute $BW = D_{total}/T$ and compare across architectures or configurations.
References	1) VAHAK: A Blockchain-based Outdoor Delivery Scheme using UAV for Healthcare 4.0 Services

Tabela 89: Metrics Catalog: Network Overhead

Metric	Network Overhead
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Relative amount of additional data transmitted in the blockchain network that does not directly correspond to user transactions, such as consensus messages, block headers, signatures, and synchronization information among nodes.
Objective	To evaluate the impact of control traffic required to maintain blockchain security, consensus, and integrity. This metric indicates how much of the network communication is consumed by protocol-level operations rather than useful application data.
Equation	$SR = \frac{D_{control}}{D_{total}}$ <p>where $D_{control}$ is the volume of control data and D_{total} is the total volume of data transmitted over the network.</p>
Comment	Lower values indicate more efficient network usage, with less bandwidth wasted on internal protocol messages. Higher values indicate that a large portion of communication is consumed by control and synchronization, which may increase latency, reduce throughput, and limit scalability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network environment and the observation interval. 2) Monitor all traffic exchanged among nodes. 3) Separate control data (consensus, headers, authentication). 4) Measure the total volume of transmitted data. 5) Compute $SR = D_{control}/D_{total}$ and compare across architectures or configurations.
References	1) Blockchain-based trusted distributed routing scheme using optimized dropout ensemble extreme learning neural network in MANET

Tabela 90: Metrics Catalog: Network Performance

Metric	Network Performance
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Overall capability of the blockchain network to transmit data and coordinate communication among its nodes efficiently, considering processing rate, resource usage, and response time under different traffic loads.
Objective	To evaluate whether the blockchain network infrastructure can sustain the communication volume required by applications while maintaining stable performance, low latency, and balanced resource utilization.
Equation	$DR = \frac{N_{req}}{T}$ <p>where N_{req} is the number of successfully processed requests or services and T is the total observation time. Higher values indicate better network performance.</p>
Comment	Higher network performance indicates that the blockchain can coordinate its nodes efficiently even under high load or partial failures. Lower values suggest communication bottlenecks, control delays, or inefficient resource usage, which may compromise scalability and system reliability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network environment and the observation period. 2) Submit requests or services to the blockchain network. 3) Record the number of successfully processed operations. 4) Measure the total execution time. 5) Compute $DR = N_{req}/T$ and compare across different configurations or architectures.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Distributed Control for Software Defined Optical Networking

Tabela 91: Metrics Catalog: Node Connectivity

Metric	Node Connectivity
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Availability
Definition	Degree of interconnection among the nodes of a blockchain network, indicating how many direct connections exist between participants. Higher connectivity facilitates transaction and block propagation, reduces communication delays, and increases network stability.
Objective	To evaluate whether the blockchain network topology provides sufficient connections among nodes to ensure good synchronization, fast information dissemination, and reduced risk of failures or forks.
Equation	$CN = \frac{\sum \text{direct connections among nodes}}{N}$ <p>where N is the total number of nodes. Higher values indicate more connected networks.</p>
Comment	High connectivity means that nodes receive blocks and transactions quickly, reducing the risk of stale states and forks. Low connectivity suggests a fragmented network with higher propagation latency and increased likelihood of temporary inconsistencies in the ledger.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify all active nodes during the observation period. 2) Measure how many direct connections each node maintains with other nodes. 3) Compute the average network connectivity. 4) Compare different connectivity configurations. 5) Relate the observed values to latency and fork occurrence.
References	1) Effect of Miner Incentive on the Confirmation Time of Bitcoin Transactions

Tabela 92: Metrics Catalog: Non-Repudiation Guarantee

Metric	Non-Repudiation Guarantee
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Non-Repudiation
Definition	Ability of a blockchain system to ensure that an action or transaction recorded cannot later be denied by its author. This guarantee is achieved through cryptographic mechanisms that verifiably bind each operation to a specific entity.
Objective	To evaluate whether the blockchain system provides sufficient mechanisms to ensure authorship and accountability for transactions, eliminating the possibility of later denial and increasing trust, auditability, and legal validity of recorded operations.
Equation	$NR = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if transactions are digitally signed and immutably recorded} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
Comment	Non-repudiation is essential for sensitive applications such as electronic auctions, digital contracts, and financial systems. When present, it ensures that participants cannot deny previously executed actions, reducing disputes and increasing trust. The absence of this mechanism compromises accountability and may lead to legal or operational conflicts.
Scale Type	Nominal
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Verify whether transactions use asymmetric cryptography-based digital signatures. 2) Confirm that each transaction is uniquely bound to a public key. 3) Evaluate whether records are stored immutably on the blockchain. 4) Test whether transaction authorship can be independently verified. 5) Assign $NR = 1$ if all conditions are met; otherwise, $NR = 0$.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof

Tabela 93: Metrics Catalog: Number of Hops

Metric	Number of Hops
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Average number of intermediate nodes through which a message (transaction or block) must pass in order to reach the majority of nodes in the blockchain network. This metric indicates how efficient the P2P network topology is for information dissemination.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of communication in the blockchain network by verifying how quickly messages can spread among nodes. A smaller number of hops tends to reduce propagation delays and improve transaction confirmation time.
Equation	$H = \frac{\sum d_i}{N},$ where d_i is the number of hops to reach node i and N is the total number of nodes reached.
Comment	Blockchain networks with well-connected topologies typically exhibit few hops between nodes, which favors fast dissemination of transactions and blocks. Low values indicate an efficient and well-structured network. High values suggest network fragmentation or low connectivity, which can increase latency and the likelihood of forks.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy monitoring nodes connected to the blockchain network. 2) Send or observe the propagation of transactions and blocks. 3) Record the reception time of messages at each node. 4) Estimate the number of hops based on arrival order and timing. 5) Compute the average number of hops across all reached nodes.
References	1) Ethna: Analyzing the Underlying Peer-to-Peer Network of Ethereum Blockchain

Tabela 94: Metrics Catalog: Number of Forwarded Blocks

Metric	Number of Forwarded Blocks
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of blocks that a blockchain node forwards to other nodes in the network during a given time interval. This metric indicates how much each node contributes to block dissemination in the peer-to-peer network.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of block propagation in the blockchain network by verifying whether nodes actively participate in forwarding information. A higher number of forwarded blocks tends to indicate good connectivity and cooperation among nodes.
Equation	$B_f = N_b/T$, where N_b is the number of forwarded blocks and T is the observed time interval.
Comment	The Number of Forwarded Blocks reflects the active role of a node in blockchain propagation. High values indicate that the node contributes to fast and balanced dissemination of blocks. Low values may indicate network bottlenecks, low connectivity, overload, or passive behavior, which can delay network synchronization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select a set of nodes in the blockchain network. 2) Monitor P2P traffic and record the blocks forwarded by each node. 3) Define the observation interval T. 4) Compute $B_f = N_b/T$ for each node. 5) Compare values across different network topologies or configurations.
References	1) A Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture Based on a Secure OpenFlow Protocol Controller Channel

Tabela 95: Metrics Catalog: Number of Lost Blocks

Metric	Number of Lost Blocks
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Total number of blocks that fail to be correctly delivered or acknowledged by nodes in the blockchain network during propagation. These blocks may be lost due to communication failures, disconnections, network overload, or temporary consensus inconsistencies.
Objective	To evaluate the reliability of the blockchain infrastructure by identifying block losses that compromise node synchronization and the consistency of the distributed ledger.
Equation	$B_{\text{lost}} = N_{\text{expected}} - N_{\text{received}}$, where N_{expected} is the number of expected blocks and N_{received} is the number of blocks actually received.
Comment	The Number of Lost Blocks indicates failures in block propagation or reception across the network. Low values reflect a stable network with reliable communication between nodes. High values suggest congestion, connectivity failures, attacks, or problems in the consensus mechanism, increasing the risk of temporary inconsistencies and reduced trust.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monitor block propagation in a real or simulated blockchain network. 2) Record the total number of expected blocks (N_{expected}) in each interval. 3) Count the blocks actually received by nodes (N_{received}). 4) Compute $B_{\text{lost}} = N_{\text{expected}} - N_{\text{received}}$. 5) Analyze the causes of losses and their relationship with load, topology, and network failures.
References	1) Health-ID: A Blockchain-Based Decentralized Identity Management for Remote Healthcare

Tabela 96: Metrics Catalog: Number of Forks per Mining Difficulty

Metric	Number of Forks per Mining Difficulty
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Relative number of forks observed in the blockchain under a given mining difficulty level. This metric expresses how variations in difficulty settings influence the occurrence of competing blocks and overall chain stability.
Objective	To assess the impact of mining difficulty on consensus stability, identifying operating ranges in which the network exhibits fewer forks and better synchronization among miners.
Equation	$F(D) = N_{\text{forks}}/N_{\text{blocks}}$, where N_{forks} is the number of observed forks, N_{blocks} is the total number of mined blocks, and D is the mining difficulty level.
Comment	This metric shows how mining difficulty adjustments affect the probability of simultaneous block creation. Very low difficulty tends to increase the occurrence of forks, as multiple miners find blocks almost at the same time. Higher difficulty reduces this competition but may increase confirmation time. A proper balance of D is essential to maintain network stability and efficiency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain to allow mining difficulty adjustments. 2) Run mining experiments under different difficulty values (D). 3) Record the total number of mined blocks (N_{blocks}). 4) Identify and count the forks that occur (N_{forks}). 5) Compute $F(D)$ for each difficulty level and compare the results.
References	1) A Decentralized Lightweight Blockchain Nodes Architecture Based on a Secure OpenFlow Protocol Controller Channel

Tabela 97: Metrics Catalog: Number of Executed Instructions

Metric	Number of Executed Instructions
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of instructions executed by a blockchain virtual machine during the execution of a smart contract or a specific function. This metric represents the computational effort required to perform a transaction.
Objective	To evaluate the computational complexity and efficiency of smart contract execution, helping identify inefficient functions and optimization opportunities to reduce execution cost and resource consumption.
Equation	I = total number of instructions executed during the execution of the evaluated contract or function.
Comment	The higher the number of executed instructions, the greater the computational cost of the transaction. This metric helps explain why certain functions consume more gas or exhibit longer execution times, even when performing logically simple operations. High values indicate more complex or poorly optimized code.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Instrument the smart contract to capture instruction execution in the virtual machine. 2) Execute the contract or function in a controlled environment (testnet or local setup). 3) Record the total number of executed instructions during execution. 4) Repeat the process for different functions or contract versions. 5) Compare the results to identify code segments with higher computational cost.
References	1) Function-Level Dynamic Monitoring and Analysis System for Smart Contract

Tabela 98: Metrics Catalog: Number of Miners

Metric	Number of Miners
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of active miners or validators in a blockchain network during the execution of the consensus protocol. This metric expresses the size of the set of nodes responsible for block validation and network maintenance.
Objective	To assess the impact of the number of miners on operational capacity, performance, and consensus robustness of the blockchain, considering the trade-off between decentralization, security, and validation efficiency.
Equation	M = total number of active miners or validators in the network during the analyzed period.
Comment	A large number of miners tends to increase decentralization and resistance to attacks, but may also raise communication costs, energy consumption, and the time required to reach consensus. Conversely, a smaller number of miners can improve latency and operational efficiency, but with a possible reduction in robustness and fault tolerance. This metric is fundamental for analyzing the trade-off between security and performance.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the total set of registered miners or validators in the network. 2) Monitor which nodes actively participate in the consensus process during the observation interval. 3) Count the total number of active miners in the analyzed period. 4) Repeat the measurement under different network configurations or consensus parameters. 5) Compare the results to assess the impact of changes in the number of miners on performance and security.
References	1) LBSS: A Lightweight Blockchain-Based Security Scheme for IoT-Enabled Healthcare Environment.

Tabela 99: Metrics Catalog: Number of Nodes

Metric	Number of Nodes
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of active nodes participating in a blockchain network or in its overlay layer, such as the Lightning Network, at a given point in time.
Objective	To assess the size, decentralization, and capacity of the network, indicating the level of participation, connectivity, and resilience of the blockchain infrastructure.
Equation	Number of Nodes = number of active nodes detected in the network during the observation period.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater participation and higher decentralization, which tends to increase network resilience. Lower values suggest node concentration and higher vulnerability to failures or censorship.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network or layer being analyzed (main blockchain or Lightning Network). 2) Run node discovery tools or network crawlers. 3) Collect the list of active nodes at regular intervals. 4) Remove duplicates and inactive nodes. 5) Count the total number of active nodes during the period.
References	1) Where is the Light(ning) in the Taproot Dawn? Unveiling the Bitcoin Lightning (IP) Network

Tabela 100: Metrics Catalog: Number of Payment Channels

Metric	Number of Payment Channels
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of active payment channels established between nodes in the Lightning Network, enabling fast and private off-chain transactions.
Objective	To assess the capacity, connectivity, and adoption level of the Lightning Network, indicating how well the infrastructure supports scalable micropayments.
Equation	Number of Payment Channels = number of active channels detected in the network during the observation period.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater connectivity and higher payment routing capacity, which favors network scalability. Lower values may indicate channel closures, reduced usage, or excessive concentration in a few nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation window of the Lightning Network. 2) Run network collection tools or crawlers. 3) Obtain the list of active channels from the network topology. 4) Remove duplicate or inactive channels. 5) Count the total number of active channels during the period.
References	1) Where is the Light(ning) in the Taproot Dawn? Unveiling the Bitcoin Lightning (IP) Network

Tabela 101: Metrics Catalog: Number of Requests

Metric	Number of Requests
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of service requests processed by a blockchain system during a given period, including transactions, queries, and smart contract executions.
Objective	To assess the capacity and scalability of the system to handle multiple simultaneous interactions, indicating the level of operational load that can be supported without significant performance degradation.
Equation	Number of Requests = total number of requests processed during the observation period.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater usage demand and higher operational capacity. Lower values may indicate underutilization, access bottlenecks, or failures in request propagation.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation window of the system. 2) Record all received and processed requests. 3) Separate valid requests from rejected requests. 4) Count the total number of requests in the period. 5) Correlate request volume with metrics such as latency and success rate.
References	1) T-DSES: A Blockchain-powered Trusted Decentralized Service Eco-System

Tabela 102: Metrics Catalog: Number of Rounds

Metric	Number of Rounds
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Number of processing rounds required for a blockchain-based system, such as a federated learning model, to reach convergence or consensus.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal efficiency of the system by indicating how many iterations are required to reach stable results, directly impacting total execution time and computational cost.
Equation	Number of Rounds = total number of iterations executed until the convergence or consensus criterion is satisfied.
Comment	A smaller number of rounds indicates faster convergence and higher system efficiency. A large number may indicate higher processing complexity, additional communication costs, or synchronization difficulties among nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Initialize the distributed system or model. 2) Define the convergence or consensus criterion. 3) Execute the processing or training rounds. 4) Check after each round whether the criterion has been met. 5) Count the total number of rounds required.
References	1) A Novel Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Industrial Internet of Medical Things

Tabela 103: Metrics Catalog: Number of Suspicious Transactions

Metric	Number of Suspicious Transactions
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Total number of transactions identified as suspicious in a blockchain network based on risk criteria defined by behavioral analysis models.
Objective	To quantify the presence of potentially fraudulent or anomalous activities in the blockchain network, supporting the identification of high-risk accounts and the monitoring of transaction integrity.
Equation	Number of Suspicious Transactions = total number of transactions whose suspicion score is greater than or equal to the threshold defined by the analysis model.
Comment	High values indicate a greater incidence of anomalous or suspicious behaviors in the network, such as potential fraud or abuse. Low values suggest a predominantly legitimate and stable environment.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collect the set of transactions from the analyzed blockchain. 2) Apply the risk analysis model to compute the suspicion score of each transaction. 3) Define a minimum threshold to classify transactions as suspicious. 4) Identify the transactions that exceed this threshold. 5) Count the total number of suspicious transactions.
References	1) A General Framework for Account Risk Rating on Ethereum: Toward Safer Blockchain Technology

Tabela 104: Metrics Catalog: Number of Voters

Metric	Number of Voters
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of people who effectively participate in a blockchain-based voting process. This metric indicates how many voters the system can support without compromising performance, security, or voting reliability.
Objective	To evaluate the capacity and scalability of blockchain voting systems by observing how increases in the number of voters affect voting time, transaction processing speed, and system resource consumption.
Equation	$NV = V $, where V represents the set of valid voters who registered or submitted votes during the voting period.
Comment	The number of voters is a central factor in assessing whether a blockchain voting system is scalable. The larger the number of participants the system can support while maintaining acceptable performance, the more suitable it is for real elections or large-scale voting.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the election process and voting period. 2) Register authorized voters in the smart contract. 3) Monitor votes submitted and validated by the network. 4) Count the total number of voters who participated. 5) Evaluate the impact of increasing the number of voters on latency, throughput, and resource usage. 6) Compare results across scenarios with different participation levels.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Voting Mechanism Underlying 5G Network: A Smart Contract Approach

Tabela 105: Metrics Catalog: Number of Write Transactions

Metric	Number of Write Transactions
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total number of transactions that perform write operations on the blockchain during an observation period, that is, transactions that insert, update, or register data and modify the network state.
Objective	To evaluate the write workload imposed on the blockchain and its impact on network capacity, execution cost, and processing time, especially in applications with frequent data recording.
Equation	Number of Write Transactions = total number of transactions that execute write operations during the analyzed period.
Comment	High values indicate intensive write activity on the blockchain, which may increase costs, latency, and resource consumption. Low values indicate lower overhead but may limit update frequency and the level of detail of recorded data.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation period of the blockchain network. 2) Identify all transactions recorded during this period. 3) Classify which transactions perform write operations (change the blockchain state). 4) Count the total number of write transactions. 5) Relate the write volume to cost, latency, and network performance.
References	1) Secure Data Exchange Between IoT Endpoints for Energy Balancing Using Distributed Ledger

Tabela 106: Metrics Catalog: Single-Miner Fork Rate

Metric	Single-Miner Fork Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of blockchain forks caused by a single miner producing more than one block at the same chain height. These events indicate situations where a miner creates redundant branches instead of competing with other participants.
Objective	To identify inefficient or selfish mining behaviors that generate unnecessary forks, waste computational resources, and affect reward fairness and network stability.
Equation	Single-Miner Fork Rate = number of forks caused by a single miner \div total number of forks in the analyzed period.
Comment	High values indicate poor miner coordination or selfish practices that increase redundant forks, reduce overall network efficiency, and raise resource consumption. Low values indicate good synchronization among miners and efficient block propagation.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain observation period. 2) Identify blocks with the same block height. 3) Determine which forks were generated by the same miner. 4) Count the number of forks caused by a single miner. 5) Divide this value by the total number of forks observed in the period.
References	1) Impact of Geo-Distribution and Mining Pools on Blockchains: A Study of Ethereum

Tabela 107: Metrics Catalog: Operation Time

Metric	Operation Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Total time required to execute an operation or transaction in a blockchain system, from the start of processing to its completion. This includes authentication, validation, and recording steps, reflecting how quickly the system responds to a request.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal efficiency and responsiveness of blockchain operations, especially in Internet of Things (IoT) applications, where long operation times may increase energy consumption and degrade system performance.
Equation	Operation Time = average of (end time – start time) over all observed operations in the period.
Comment	Shorter operation times indicate faster and more efficient systems suitable for delay-sensitive applications. High values suggest processing bottlenecks, excessive validation steps, or communication overhead between nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the set of operations to be evaluated. 2) Record the start and end time of each operation. 3) Compute the individual operation time. 4) Calculate the average over the observation period. 5) Compare results across different configurations or protocols.
References	1) BENIGREEN: Blockchain-Based Energy-Efficient Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Green IoT

Tabela 108: Metrics Catalog: Out-of-Gas Exception Rate

Metric	Out-of-Gas Exception Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of transactions or smart contract calls that fail because the allocated gas was not sufficient to complete execution. When an out-of-gas event occurs, execution is halted, state is reverted, and the transaction fee is consumed.
Objective	To evaluate operation reliability and the quality of gas estimation used by contracts, wallets, and applications. This metric helps reduce failed transactions, improve user experience, and prevent errors caused by under-provisioned gas.
Equation	$\text{OOG Rate} = \frac{\text{Number of transactions that failed due to out of gas}}{\text{Total number of transactions}}$ <p>Optionally, a gas safety margin per transaction can be computed as:</p> $H = 1 - (\text{gas_used}/\text{gas_limit}).$
Comment	Low values indicate predictable contracts and good gas estimation. High values suggest gas underestimation, heavy storage usage, input-dependent loops, or recent code changes. This metric is independent of gas price and depends only on allocated gas.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the analysis period and the set of contracts or functions to be evaluated. 2) Collect transaction receipts executed during the period. 3) Identify transactions that explicitly failed due to out-of-gas. 4) Compute the out-of-gas exception rate for the overall period and per function. 5) Analyze trends after code or input parameter changes. 6) Adjust gas limits and safety buffers to reduce future failures.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Ethereum: A Secure Decentralised Generalised Transaction Ledger (Yellow Paper) 2) Ethereum Improvement Proposals (EIP-150, EIP-1559)

Tabela 109: Metrics Catalog: Overhead Ratio

Metric	Overhead Ratio
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Proportion of additional resources consumed by a system when extra mechanisms, such as blockchain, authentication, or cryptography, are enabled compared to a baseline version without these mechanisms. Overhead may involve execution time, processing, communication, or energy consumption.
Objective	To assess the operational impact introduced by security and blockchain mechanisms, enabling comparison between lightweight and heavy solutions and supporting the selection of more efficient architectures for distributed systems, especially in IoT environments.
Equation	$R_o = \frac{C_{total} - C_{base}}{C_{base}},$ <p>where C_{total} is the cost with the additional mechanism enabled and C_{base} is the cost of the baseline system without that mechanism.</p>
Comment	Low values indicate that the additional mechanism imposes little penalty on the system. High values suggest that the solution introduces excessive overhead, potentially compromising performance, scalability, or energy efficiency. This metric does not evaluate security directly, but the cost of achieving it.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the baseline system scenario without additional mechanisms. 2) Measure the cost of the baseline system (time, processing, communication, or energy). 3) Enable the blockchain or authentication mechanism. 4) Measure the total cost again under the same conditions. 5) Compute the overhead ratio using the defined equation. 6) Compare results across different protocols or configurations.
References	1) A Lightweight Blockchain-Based Remote Mutual Authentication for AI-Empowered IoT Sustainable Computing Systems

Tabela 110: Metrics Catalog: Control Centralization Index

Metric	Control Centralization Index
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of smart contract functions that grant special privileges to a single entity, such as the owner or administrator. These functions allow modifying, pausing, or reconfiguring contract behavior, indicating the degree of control centralization.
Objective	To assess centralization risk in smart contracts by identifying situations where a single entity has excessive power over rules, parameters, or assets, which may compromise trust and system decentralization.
Equation	$CCI = \frac{N_{\text{privileged functions}}}{N_{\text{total functions}}},$ <p>where $N_{\text{privileged functions}}$ is the number of functions with restricted access (e.g., <code>onlyOwner</code> or <code>admin</code>) and $N_{\text{total functions}}$ is the total number of public contract functions.</p>
Comment	High values indicate greater concentration of power and higher risk of abuse, censorship, or unilateral contract changes. Low values suggest more decentralized contracts with more stable rules and less reliance on trust in a single actor.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select smart contracts for analysis. 2) Inspect the source code or use auditing tools to identify access modifiers. 3) Classify functions as privileged or non-privileged. 4) Count the total number of functions and the number of privileged ones. 5) Compute the CCI using the defined equation.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 111: Metrics Catalog: Packet Loss Rate

Metric	Packet Loss Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of data packets that fail to reach their destination during communication between nodes in a blockchain network. Losses may occur due to routing failures, congestion, network attacks, or temporary disconnections.
Objective	To evaluate the reliability of node-to-node communication in distributed blockchain environments, especially when integrated with Software-Defined Networking (SDN), by identifying the impact of routing failures and attacks on data transmission.
Equation	Packet Loss Rate = $\frac{N_{\text{lost packets}}}{N_{\text{sent packets}}} \times 100$.
Comment	Low rates indicate stable and reliable communication between nodes. High rates suggest network problems such as congestion, routing attacks, or infrastructure failures, which can compromise blockchain consensus and system availability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the network scenario and observation window. 2) Transmit data packets between blockchain nodes under normal and adverse conditions. 3) Record the total number of packets sent. 4) Record the number of packets that did not reach their destination. 5) Compute the packet loss rate using the defined equation.
References	1) SDBGPChain: A Decentralized Low Complexity Framework to Detect and Prevent the BGP Attacks using SDN with Smart Contract-Based Dendrimer Tree Blockchain

Tabela 112: Metrics Catalog: Packet Loss Index

Metric	Packet Loss Index
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Total number of data packets that fail to reach their destination during transmission between nodes in a blockchain network. This is an absolute measure of communication loss, independent of the total volume of packets sent.
Objective	To quantify the absolute volume of communication losses between blockchain nodes, supporting the identification of bottlenecks, structural failures, and critical nodes that affect the propagation of messages, blocks, and transactions.
Equation	Packet Loss Index = $N_{\text{sent packets}} - N_{\text{received packets}}$.
Comment	Lower values indicate more stable and reliable communication. High values suggest structural network problems such as node failures, persistent congestion, or attacks, which may compromise block propagation and consensus stability. This index is often used as a basis for computing relative metrics such as Packet Loss Rate.
Scale Type	Absolute
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the blockchain network topology and observation window. 2) Transmit data packets between nodes under normal and failure conditions. 3) Record the total number of packets sent. 4) Record the total number of packets successfully received. 5) Compute the packet loss index as the difference between sent and received packets.
References	1) Node Criticality Assessment in a Blockchain Network

Tabela 113: Metrics Catalog: Penalty Rate

Metric	Penalty Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Measure of the number of penalties accumulated by a peer-to-peer energy trading agent in a blockchain and reinforcement learning (Q-learning) environment. It represents the number of incorrect decisions, inefficient transactions, or policy violations that result in punishments assigned to the agent during the learning process.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency and stability of the reinforcement learning algorithm in reducing incorrect behaviors and improving agent decision-making in blockchain systems. A lower penalty rate indicates learning convergence and higher trading reliability.
Equation	$P_r = \frac{N_{\text{penalties}}}{N_{\text{episodes}}},$ <p>where $N_{\text{penalties}}$ is the total number of penalties assigned to the agent and N_{episodes} is the total number of learning episodes.</p>
Comment	During training, the agent is expected to reduce the number of penalties as it learns optimal trading policies. A high initial rate is normal, followed by stabilization as the model converges. This metric is essential for measuring learning quality and the efficiency of agent adaptation in decentralized energy blockchain networks. Low values indicate efficient learning and stable decisions, while high values suggest poor adaptation or a poorly configured learning environment.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the PRS-P2P environment with prosumer agents (buyers and sellers). 2) Run multiple reinforcement learning episodes using Q-learning. 3) Assign penalties for each incorrect decision (e.g., wrong seller selection, energy limit violations, transaction delays). 4) Count $N_{\text{penalties}}$ and normalize by the number of episodes N_{episodes}. 5) Record the evolution of the rate over training to measure agent convergence.
References	Kumari, A.; Gupta, R.; Tanwar, S. PRS-P2P: A Prosumer Recommender System for Secure P2P Energy Trading using Q-Learning. Towards 6G. IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops), 2021.

Tabela 114: Metrics Catalog: Resource Performance

Metric	Resource Performance
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Level of efficiency obtained from the use of computational resources, such as CPU and memory, during the execution of operations in a blockchain system. This metric indicates whether the system can process its tasks while maintaining a balanced use of available resources.
Objective	To evaluate whether the blockchain system maintains good operational performance without overloading CPU and memory, supporting analyses of efficiency, scalability, and practical viability in data-intensive applications such as electronic health record systems.
Equation	$\text{Resource Performance} = \frac{\text{Average CPU usage} + \text{Average memory usage}}{2}$
Comment	Lower values indicate more efficient use of resources, provided the system maintains adequate functional performance. Very high utilization may signal bottlenecks, risk of performance degradation, or scalability limitations. This metric should be analyzed together with the workload volume.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain system to be evaluated. 2) Execute a controlled set of operations (e.g., transactions or records). 3) Continuously monitor CPU and memory usage during execution. 4) Compute the average CPU and memory usage over the observation period. 5) Apply the equation to obtain the resource performance metric.
References	1) A Novel Blockchain-Based Electronic Health Record Automation System for Healthcare

Tabela 115: Metrics Catalog: Performance Across Different Machines

Metric	Performance Across Different Machines
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Variation in the execution time of transactions or smart contracts when run on machines with different hardware capabilities, such as CPU, memory, and architecture. This metric evaluates how much perceived performance depends on the physical environment where the blockchain node is executed.
Objective	To assess whether hardware differences influence blockchain operation execution time, supporting analyses of portability, performance predictability, and appropriate infrastructure selection for running and testing smart contracts.
Equation	$\text{Relative Performance} = \frac{\text{Average execution time on the reference machine}}{\text{Average execution time on the evaluated machine}}$
Comment	Values greater than 1 indicate that the evaluated machine executes operations faster than the reference machine. Small differences suggest that the blockchain platform provides good abstraction from underlying hardware. Large differences indicate strong dependence on the physical environment, which may affect testing, debugging, and operational performance.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select two or more machines with different hardware configurations. 2) Define a reference machine. 3) Execute the same set of transactions or smart contracts on all machines under identical network conditions. 4) Measure the average execution time in each environment. 5) Compute relative performance by comparing each machine against the reference.
References	1) Empirically Analyzing Ethereum's Gas Mechanism

Tabela 116: Metrics Catalog: Unhandled Exception Rate

Metric	Unhandled Exception Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of exceptions generated in a blockchain system that are not properly handled, resulting in execution failures, service interruptions, or temporary inconsistencies in system state.
Objective	To evaluate the robustness of error handling in distributed blockchain systems by identifying weaknesses in exception management that may compromise operational integrity and service continuity.
Equation	$E_{ph} = \frac{N_{\text{unhandled}}}{N_{\text{total}}}$
Comment	High values indicate poor exception handling, increasing the risk of cascading failures, transaction validation interruptions, or performance degradation. Low values suggest that the system can effectively capture, isolate, and recover from exceptions, maintaining operational integrity.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Run the blockchain system under different loads and failure scenarios. 2) Record all exceptions detected during execution. 3) Identify which exceptions were properly handled and which were not. 4) Compute the ratio of unhandled exceptions to the total number of exceptions. 5) Analyze logs to identify recurring patterns and critical points in error handling.
References	1) An Efficient Distributed and Secure Algorithm for Transaction Confirmation in IOTA Using Cloud Computing

Tabela 117: Metrics Catalog: Consumption Price

Metric	Consumption Price
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Minimum transaction fee that a user must pay for a transaction to be accepted and processed by the blockchain within an acceptable time. This value represents the minimum cost of accessing the network at a given moment.
Objective	To evaluate the stability and fairness of the minimum cost required to process transactions in a blockchain. This metric helps identify congestion, supply–demand imbalances for block space, and opportunistic behavior in transaction prioritization.
Equation	$f_{min} = \min(f_{txn})$, subject to processing latency $\leq L_{max}$.
Comment	Low and stable values of f_{min} indicate a balanced network in which users can predict costs reliably. High or highly variable values indicate congestion, backlog accumulation, and degraded user experience. Unlike total transaction cost, consumption price reflects only the minimum fee required for acceptance, not the fee actually paid.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Operate the blockchain under stable conditions. 2) Monitor the transactions included in each block. 3) Identify the lowest fee paid among confirmed transactions. 4) Record the evolution of f_{min} over time. 5) Analyze the variation of f_{min} with respect to mempool size and miner selection behavior.
References	1) BitcoinF: Achieving Fairness for Bitcoin in Transaction-Fee-Only Model

Tabela 118: Metrics Catalog: Cost Savings

Metric	Cost Savings
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Monetary value saved by consumers and providers after adopting a blockchain-based demand response management scheme. This metric compares total energy cost before and after the application of the proposed mechanism.
Objective	To evaluate the financial benefits obtained through the use of smart contracts and economic incentives for energy demand management. This metric indicates the economic viability of the system and its ability to reduce operational and consumption costs.
Equation	$Savings = \sum (C_{base}(i) - C_{drm}(i)).$
Comment	Higher values indicate greater economic benefit generated by the demand response management scheme. This metric reflects aggregated financial gains over time and does not represent the cost of a single transaction or unit of energy. Low values may indicate low consumer participation or limited impact of the load redistribution mechanism.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collect energy consumption data at regular intervals. 2) Compute the total cost without the management scheme (C_{base}). 3) Apply the blockchain-based demand response mechanism. 4) Compute the total cost after the scheme (C_{drm}). 5) Compute the aggregated difference between C_{base} and C_{drm} as cost savings.
References	1) A Data Analytics Scheme for Security-aware Demand Response Management in Smart Grid System

Tabela 119: Metrics Catalog: Private Key Leakage Rate

Metric	Private Key Leakage Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Confidentiality
Definition	Frequency at which private keys are exposed or compromised in blockchain systems. This metric reflects security failures in wallets, exchanges, and custody services that store or manage users' cryptographic keys.
Objective	To quantify the risk of private key compromise in blockchain ecosystems, especially those relying on centralized components. The metric supports security assessment of providers and helps identify single points of failure.
Equation	Leakage Rate = $\frac{\text{Number of compromised private keys}}{\text{Total number of stored private keys}}$.
Comment	High values indicate weak private key management and a high risk to asset confidentiality. This metric is strongly influenced by the degree of custody centralization. Mechanisms such as non-custodial wallets, multisignature schemes, and key sharding significantly reduce the risk of key leakage.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify platforms or services that store or manage users' private keys. 2) Collect documented incidents of key exposure, theft, or leakage. 3) Count the number of compromised keys during the analysis period. 4) Compute the leakage rate relative to the total number of managed keys. 5) Analyze the causes of incidents to contextualize the results.

Tabela 120: Metrics Catalog: Query Time

Metric	Query Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time elapsed between the request and the complete reception of the response to a query on data stored in the blockchain. This metric evaluates the system's read performance when retrieving transaction or smart contract information.
Objective	To assess the temporal efficiency of data access in blockchain networks, especially in Internet of Things applications, where read delays directly affect responsiveness and near-real-time operation.
Equation	$\text{AverageTime} = (1/N) \times \sum(t_{\text{response}_i} - t_{\text{request}_i}).$
Comment	Query time is influenced by the consensus mechanism, the block data structure, and the capacity of the nodes serving requests. Mechanisms with shorter block times and simpler validation tend to provide lower and more stable query times.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain under different consensus mechanisms. 2) Record a set of transactions or smart contracts. 3) Execute read queries on the stored data using a blockchain access API. 4) Measure the time between request submission and complete response reception. 5) Compute the average query time for each analyzed configuration.

Tabela 121: Metrics Catalog: RAM Utilization

Metric	RAM Utilization
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of RAM memory used by blockchain network nodes during their operation. This metric indicates how intensively the system consumes memory to keep the blockchain running.
Objective	To evaluate whether memory consumption is efficient and predictable during blockchain operation, supporting proper infrastructure sizing and the identification of bottlenecks in resource-constrained devices.
Equation	$\text{RAM Utilization (\%)} = (\text{RAM}_{\text{used}} / \text{RAM}_{\text{total}}) \times 100.$
Comment	RAM utilization mainly reflects node software behavior and the active processing load. Stable memory consumption indicates good efficiency and facilitates running the blockchain on low-cost or resource-limited devices.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monitor RAM usage of each network node during normal blockchain operation. 2) Periodically record the amount of RAM used and the total available memory. 3) Compute the average RAM utilization over time. 4) Compare results across different device types and transaction loads. 5) Analyze consumption stability as the blockchain grows.

Tabela 122: Metrics Catalog: Stale Block Rate

Metric	Stale Block Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of mined blocks that are not incorporated into the main blockchain. These blocks, called stale or orphaned blocks, arise when there are delays in block propagation across the network.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of block propagation and the impact of network latency on the security and performance of consensus. A high rate indicates wasted computational effort and greater chain instability.
Equation	Stale Block Rate = $(N_{\text{stale blocks}}/N_{\text{total blocks}}) \times 100$.
Comment	Stale blocks represent wasted mining work and reduce the overall efficiency of the network. High rates are typically associated with large blocks, propagation delays, or inefficient block dissemination mechanisms.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monitor all mined blocks during an observation period. 2) Identify which blocks were not included in the main chain. 3) Count the total number of blocks and the number of stale blocks. 4) Compute the stale block rate using the defined equation. 5) Compare results under different network conditions and propagation mechanisms.

Tabela 123: Metrics Catalog: Opcode Execution Rate

Metric	Opcode Execution Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Ratio between the actual time required to execute an Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) opcode and the gas cost assigned to that opcode. This metric indicates whether the gas cost properly reflects the real computational effort.
Objective	To assess whether EVM opcodes are correctly priced in terms of gas, identifying instructions that consume more or less execution time than expected. This helps improve performance predictability and the balance of the blockchain cost model.
Equation	Opcode Execution Rate = Execution Time/Gas Cost.
Comment	When an opcode takes a long time to execute but has a low gas cost, it can be exploited to generate network overload. Conversely, opcodes with high cost and fast execution tend to be overpriced. This metric helps reveal such imbalances.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Instrument an Ethereum client to collect opcode-level execution data. 2) Measure the real execution time of each opcode during contract execution. 3) Associate each opcode with its official EVM gas cost. 4) Compute the ratio between execution time and gas cost for each opcode. 5) Compare values across opcodes to identify significant discrepancies.

Tabela 124: Metrics Catalog: Reentrancy Vulnerability Rate

Metric	Reentrancy Vulnerability Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of functions or smart contracts that exhibit risk of reentrancy attacks. This type of vulnerability occurs when a contract allows external calls before completing its internal state updates, enabling the same function to be executed repeatedly in an unintended manner.
Objective	To assess the level of exposure of smart contracts to reentrancy attacks, supporting security audits and the identification of flaws that compromise transaction and contract state integrity.
Equation	Reentrancy Rate = (Vulnerable Functions/Analyzed Functions) × 100.
Comment	Reentrancy vulnerabilities usually arise when contracts perform external calls before updating internal state variables. This flaw can allow multiple unintended executions of the same function, resulting in financial losses or contract state corruption.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select the smart contracts to be evaluated. 2) Identify functions that perform external calls. 3) Apply static analysis tools to detect reentrancy patterns. 4) Count the identified vulnerable functions. 5) Compute the vulnerability rate relative to the total number of analyzed functions.

Tabela 125: Metrics Catalog: Reliability Rate

Metric	Reliability Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Availability
Definition	Proportion of operations or transactions that are successfully executed by a blockchain system, without failures, relative to the total number of requested operations.
Objective	To assess how reliable and stable the operation of the blockchain system is, indicating its ability to correctly execute tasks and transactions even under load or partial failures.
Equation	Reliability Rate = Number of successful operations/Total number of operations
Comment	Higher values indicate a more stable and predictable system. Low rates suggest frequent execution failures, consensus problems, overload, or node unavailability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the set of operations or transactions to be evaluated. 2) Execute the operations in the blockchain system during an observation period. 3) Record the total number of requested operations. 4) Record the number of successfully completed operations. 5) Compute the ratio between successful and total operations.
References	1) Decentralized Blockchain-Based and Trust-Aware Task Offloading Strategy for Healthcare IoT

Tabela 126: Metrics Catalog: Request Success Rate

Metric	Request Success Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of requests or transactions that are successfully processed by a blockchain system relative to the total number of submitted requests.
Objective	To assess the ability of the blockchain system to correctly respond to service requests, indicating the robustness of inter-node communication and processing stability under different load conditions.
Equation	Request Success Rate = Number of successful requests/Total number of requests.
Comment	High values indicate a reliable system with good coordination among nodes and a low incidence of failures. Drops in this rate suggest overload, consensus failures, timeouts, or network instability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the set of requests or transactions to be evaluated. 2) Send the requests to the blockchain system during an observation period. 3) Record the total number of issued requests. 4) Record the number of requests completed with a valid response. 5) Compute the ratio between successful and total requests.
References	1) T-DSES: A Blockchain-powered Trusted Decentralized Service Eco-System

Tabela 127: Metrics Catalog: Residual Energy Ratio

Metric	Residual Energy Ratio
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Proportion of the remaining energy available in a node or vehicle after executing communication, computation, and blockchain recording tasks, relative to the total energy initially available.
Objective	To evaluate the energy efficiency of the blockchain system, indicating how much of the available energy is consumed by operations and whether nodes or vehicles can maintain adequate autonomy during operation.
Equation	Residual Energy Ratio = Residual Energy/Initial Total Energy.
Comment	High values indicate that the system consumes little energy to perform its functions. Low values suggest high energy consumption, which may compromise autonomy and service continuity, especially in vehicular and IoT networks.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the initial total energy available in each node or vehicle. 2) Execute communication, processing, and blockchain recording tasks. 3) Measure the residual energy after task execution. 4) Compute the ratio between residual energy and initial total energy. 5) Repeat the procedure under different loads and network topologies.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Matching Game for Content Sharing in Content-Centric Vehicle-to-Grid Network Scenarios

Tabela 128: Metrics Catalog: Resource Consumption

Metric	Resource Consumption
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Amount of computational resources used by a blockchain application or network to execute its operations, including CPU, memory, disk, network, and storage, both on-chain and off-chain.
Objective	To evaluate resource-use efficiency, identify bottlenecks, and support decisions on capacity planning, optimization, and operational cost reduction in blockchain-based solutions.
Equation	Resource consumption over a period = ⟨CPU, Memory, Disk, Network, Storage⟩. Normalized form: Consumption per transaction = total consumption over the period / number of confirmed transactions.
Comment	Lower resource consumption for the same performance level (TPS and latency) indicates higher efficiency. Architectures that use off-chain storage tend to reduce on-chain disk usage at the cost of higher network utilization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the measurement period and the evaluated operations (read, write, deploy). 2) Run controlled workloads and record the number of confirmed transactions. 3) Collect CPU, memory, disk, and network metrics from participating nodes. 4) Measure on-chain storage growth and, when applicable, off-chain storage usage. 5) Compute total consumption and average consumption per transaction. 6) Compare scenarios and record environment and workload conditions.
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hyperledger Healthchain: Patient-Centric IPFS-Based Storage of Health Records 2) HealthBlock: A Secure Blockchain-Based Healthcare Data Management System

Tabela 129: Metrics Catalog: System Responsiveness Rate

Metric	System Responsiveness Rate
Characteristic	Usability
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Proportion of requests that receive a response from the blockchain system within an acceptable time limit, reflecting the promptness and responsiveness perceived by users or client systems.
Objective	To assess the ability of the blockchain system to respond quickly to requests, ensuring an adequate user experience and response times compatible with service requirements.
Equation	$\text{Responsiveness Rate} = \frac{\text{Number of requests answered within the time limit}}{\text{Total number of requests}}$
Comment	High values indicate that the system responds quickly to most requests. Low values suggest slowdowns, processing overload, blockchain growth, or limitations in the consensus mechanism.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the maximum acceptable response time for the service. 2) Send a set of requests to the blockchain system. 3) Measure the response time of each request. 4) Count how many requests were answered within the time limit. 5) Compute the ratio between timely responses and total requests.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Access Control and Data Sharing Mechanism in Cloud Decentralized Storage System

Tabela 130: Metrics Catalog: RPC Centralization Risk

Metric	RPC Centralization Risk
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Proportion of wallets or decentralized applications that depend on a single centralized RPC provider to access the blockchain network, indicating the degree of access infrastructure concentration.
Objective	To assess the risk introduced by reliance on centralized RPC providers, which may cause service outages, censorship, or loss of network access, undermining the functional decentralization of the ecosystem.
Equation	$\text{RPC Centralization Risk} = \frac{\text{Number of applications dependent on centralized RPC}}{\text{Total number of applications}}$
Comment	High values indicate strong dependence on a small number of RPC providers, increasing the risk of unavailability and censorship. Low values indicate more resilient ecosystems with multiple configurable providers or self-hosted nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the most widely used wallets and decentralized applications in the analyzed ecosystem. 2) Verify which RPC provider each application uses by default. 3) Determine whether the provider is unique and not configurable by the user. 4) Count how many applications depend exclusively on centralized RPC. 5) Compute the ratio between dependent applications and the total analyzed.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 131: Metrics Catalog: Self-Balancing Index

Metric	Self-Balancing Index
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Recoverability
Definition	Measures the ability of a sharded blockchain to maintain or restore a balanced distribution of nodes across shards after participants join or leave the network.
Objective	To assess whether the protocol can automatically redistribute nodes across shards, preventing some shards from becoming overloaded while others remain underpopulated.
Equation	$\text{Self-Balancing Index} = 1 - \frac{\text{largest difference in the number of nodes between shards}}{\text{average number of nodes per shard}}$
Comment	Values close to 1 indicate that shards have similar sizes, which reduces bottlenecks, improves overall performance, and lowers security risks. Low values indicate imbalance, with potential negative impacts on performance and security.
Scale Type	Interval
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the number of shards in the network. 2) Run the system under churn events, with nodes joining and leaving. 3) Measure the number of nodes in each shard at the end of each period. 4) Compute the average number of nodes per shard. 5) Identify the largest difference between shard sizes. 6) Apply the equation to obtain the index.
References	1) Analysing and Improving Shard Allocation Protocols for Sharded Blockchains

Tabela 132: Metrics Catalog: Signature Creation Time

Metric	Signature Creation Time
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Measures the time required to generate a digital signature using a private key and attach it to a transaction or data item in a blockchain system.
Objective	To assess the efficiency of the cryptographic authentication process, verifying whether digital signature generation is fast enough for time-sensitive applications such as medical and industrial systems.
Equation	Signature Creation Time = end timestamp – start timestamp.
Comment	Lower values indicate a more efficient signing process with less impact on overall transaction time. High values may increase system latency and limit the use of blockchain in applications that require fast responses.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Select the digital signature algorithm used. 2) Define the size of the data to be signed. 3) Record the timestamp when signature generation starts. 4) Record the timestamp when signature generation is completed. 5) Compute the elapsed time between the two timestamps. 6) Repeat the procedure and compute mean and variability.
References	1) A Novel Homomorphic Encryption and Consortium Blockchain-Based Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Industrial Internet of Medical Things

Tabela 133: Metrics Catalog: Static Service Rate

Metric	Static Service Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Measures the maximum number of transactions that an ordering node can process per second when operating under a fixed configuration, without dynamic adjustments during execution.
Objective	To evaluate the processing capacity of the ordering service, determining whether the infrastructure can support the expected transaction volume or whether there is a risk of queue buildup and delays.
Equation	Static Service Rate (μ) = $1/T_s$, where T_s is the average time required by the node to process a transaction.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater processing capacity and lower risk of congestion. When the transaction arrival rate approaches or exceeds this rate, the system tends to experience longer queues and increased latency.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the ordering node and keep configuration parameters fixed. 2) Submit a controlled stream of transactions to the system. 3) Measure the average time required to process each transaction. 4) Compute the static service rate using the equation. 5) Compare the obtained rate with the transaction arrival rate to assess overload risk.
References	1) Performance Evaluation of M/D/1 Queuing Model on Hyperledger Fabric

Tabela 134: Metrics Catalog: Storage Usage

Metric	Storage Usage
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Measures the average amount of storage space or memory used by a blockchain system during data processing and validation.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of storage usage in blockchain solutions, supporting scalability analysis and infrastructure cost planning, especially in cloud environments.
Equation	Storage Usage = average amount of memory or disk space used during operation, typically measured in MB.
Comment	Lower values indicate more efficient use of storage resources. High consumption may signal overload, the need for data optimization, or excessive use of cryptographic mechanisms and auxiliary data structures.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the blockchain solution to be evaluated. 2) Run processing and validation operations under different loads. 3) Monitor memory or disk space consumption during execution. 4) Compute the average storage usage. 5) Compare results across different solutions or configurations.
References	1) Optimization with Blockchain-Based Secure Authentication and Collaborative Data Sharing Model in Cloud

Tabela 135: Metrics Catalog: Success and Failure Rate

Metric	Success and Failure Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Measures the proportion of transactions successfully completed and the proportion of transactions that fail during execution in a blockchain system.
Objective	To evaluate the operational reliability of the blockchain network, verifying whether the system can execute transactions stably under different loads and fault conditions.
Equation	Success Rate = $(N_{\text{success}}/N_{\text{total}}) \times 100$
Failure Rate = $(N_{\text{failures}}/N_{\text{total}}) \times 100$	
Comment	High success rates indicate that the network is operating in a stable and fault-tolerant manner. An increase in the failure rate may indicate congestion, synchronization problems among nodes, or limitations in the consensus configuration.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Record all transactions submitted to the blockchain network during a defined interval. 2) Identify which transactions were successfully confirmed and which failed. 3) Count the total number of transactions, successes, and failures. 4) Compute the success and failure rates using the equations. 5) Compare the results under different network loads and configurations.
References	1) Hyperledger Healthchain: Patient-centric IPFS-based Storage of Health Records

Tabela 136: Metrics Catalog: Success Probability

Metric	Success Probability
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Measures the probability that a transaction is successfully transmitted and validated in a blockchain network, considering message losses, packet collisions, and the number of nodes participating in consensus.
Objective	To assess the reliability of the consensus process and network communication, verifying whether the system can correctly validate transactions even in the presence of failures and interference.
Equation	$P_s = \frac{n \times \tau \times (1 - \tau)^{n-1}}{1 - (1 - \tau)^n}.$ <p>Where τ is the probability that a node attempts to transmit in a time slot and n is the total number of nodes.</p> <p>The overall consensus success probability is obtained by combining the PBFT protocol phases (prepare and commit), considering the minimum number of correct nodes required.</p>
Comment	High values indicate that the network can reliably validate transactions even in the presence of communication failures. As the number of nodes grows or collisions increase, the success probability tends to decrease, revealing scalability limits of the consensus.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the number of nodes participating in consensus. 2) Estimate the per-node transmission attempt probability. 3) Compute the probability of successful transmission. 4) Combine consensus phases to obtain the total success probability. 5) Evaluate the impact of different network sizes and interference levels.
References	1) Performance Analysis of Wireless Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance Networks Using IEEE 802.11

Tabela 137: Metrics Catalog: System Cost

Metric	System Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Measures the total operational cost of a blockchain system, including expenses related to contract deployment, function execution, data storage, and recurring transactions. The cost is expressed based on gas consumption and its conversion into monetary value.
Objective	To evaluate the economic feasibility and operational efficiency of blockchain systems, enabling comparison across architectures and identification of financial impacts arising from smart contract usage.
Equation	System Cost = $\sum(\text{GasUsed}_i \times \text{GasPrice})$ + additional transaction and storage costs.
Comment	Lower costs indicate higher economic efficiency of the system. The total cost is influenced by function complexity, execution frequency, stored data volume, and prevailing gas market conditions.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the smart contract in the target environment. 2) Execute all relevant system operations. 3) Record the gas consumption of each operation. 4) Convert total gas usage into monetary value using the average gas price. 5) Compare results across different configurations or solutions.
References	1) SmartMeasurer: A Secure and Automated Bandwidth Measurement for Tor with Smart Contract.

Tabela 138: Metrics Catalog: System Operability Index

Metric	System Operability Index
Characteristic	Usability
Subcharacteristic	Operability
Definition	Measures how well a sharded blockchain system continues to operate in a stable and efficient manner during network changes, such as shard reallocation, node churn, and load variations.
Objective	To assess the operational capability of the sharding protocol to maintain performance and availability during reconfigurations, indicating how easy the system is to operate and maintain in dynamic environments.
Equation	System Operability Index (IO_s) = $R_{\text{stability}} / (T_{\text{reconfig}} \times C_{\text{coord}})$, where $R_{\text{stability}}$ is the proportion of shards that remain operational and stable after reallocation, T_{reconfig} is the average time required to complete shard reconfiguration, and C_{coord} is the average coordination and communication cost between shards during the process.
Comment	Higher index values indicate that the system can reorganize quickly, with low coordination effort among shards and maintained stability. Low values suggest that reconfigurations cause delays, high coordination overhead, or operational instability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Implement the shard allocation protocol. 2) Simulate shard reallocation events and changes in the number of nodes. 3) Measure system stability after reconfiguration. 4) Measure the time required for reconfiguration. 5) Measure the coordination cost between shards. 6) Compute the operability index and compare across different protocols.
References	1) Analysing and Improving Shard Allocation Protocols for Sharded Blockchains

Tabela 139: Metrics Catalog: Third-Party SDK Integration Risk

Metric	Third-Party SDK Integration Risk
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Confidentiality
Definition	Measures the level of risk introduced by dependence on third-party SDKs and libraries in blockchain applications such as wallets and DApps. This metric evaluates the potential exposure of sensitive data, loss of privacy, and indirect centralization when external components access, process, or transmit user information.
Objective	To assess the impact of integrating external SDKs on security and confidentiality in blockchain ecosystems, identifying dependencies that may compromise user privacy, introduce single points of failure, or enable tracking and censorship.
Equation	$RSDK = (N_{\text{risk SDKs}} / N_{\text{total SDKs}}) \times 100,$ <p>where $N_{\text{risk SDKs}}$ is the number of third-party SDKs classified as potentially risky (e.g., collecting sensitive data, tracking, centralized authentication, or communication with external servers) and $N_{\text{total SDKs}}$ is the total number of SDKs integrated into the analyzed application.</p>
Comment	High RSDK values indicate greater exposure to privacy and centralization risks, as they increase the attack surface and dependence on external infrastructure. Analytics, authentication, and notification SDKs are common sources of this risk. Reducing the number of external SDKs tends to improve confidentiality and adherence to decentralization principles.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the blockchain application to be analyzed (e.g., wallet or DApp). 2) Extract and decompile the application to list all integrated libraries and SDKs. 3) Classify SDKs as internal or third-party. 4) Assess which SDKs exhibit risky behavior (collection, transmission, or processing of sensitive data). 5) Compute the percentage of risky SDKs relative to the total integrated.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 140: Metrics Catalog: Ledger Pruning Time

Metric	Ledger Pruning Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required to remove old or unnecessary data from the blockchain ledger, freeing storage space without compromising network security or integrity.
Objective	To evaluate the efficiency of the ledger maintenance mechanism, ensuring that storage growth is controlled and that network performance remains stable over time.
Equation	$T_{\text{prune}} = \text{pruning end time} - \text{pruning start time}.$
Comment	Shorter pruning times indicate more efficient ledger maintenance. Long times may reveal storage bottlenecks, low disk read/write throughput, or inefficient protocol design.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Enable or observe the pruning process on a blockchain node. 2) Record the time at which pruning starts. 3) Record the time at which pruning ends. 4) Compute the difference between the two timestamps to obtain the pruning time. 5) Repeat the measurement across different nodes or runs for comparative analysis.
References	1) Bitcoin-NG: A Scalable Blockchain Protocol

Tabela 141: Metrics Catalog: Time to Win

Metric	Time to Win
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for a node or miner to produce a winning block, measured from the start of the mining attempt to the discovery of a valid block accepted by the network.
Objective	To evaluate how quickly the consensus protocol selects a new winning block, enabling analysis of the efficiency and responsiveness of consensus mechanisms, especially in architectures such as Bitcoin-NG.
Equation	T_{win} = time of winning block discovery – time when mining attempt starts.
Comment	Shorter times indicate higher efficiency of the mining process and faster propagation of the winning block. Higher values may indicate high difficulty, concentration of computational power, network congestion, or connectivity problems.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Track mining logs or events from network nodes. 2) Record the time when each mining attempt starts. 3) Record the time when the winning block is discovered. 4) Compute the time to win for each observed event. 5) Analyze statistics such as mean, median, and percentiles to compare nodes or configurations.
References	1) Bitcoin-NG: A Scalable Blockchain Protocol

Tabela 142: Metrics Catalog: Reward Time Steps

Metric	Reward Time Steps
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Number of time steps required for a reinforcement learning algorithm integrated with a blockchain system to reach a stable or target reward level.
Objective	To evaluate how quickly reinforcement learning algorithms converge to stable decisions when applied in blockchain-based applications, such as peer-to-peer energy trading systems.
Equation	T_{reward} = minimum number of time steps until the accumulated reward reaches a defined stable level.
Comment	Fewer time steps indicate more efficient learning. Higher values suggest slow convergence, unstable decision policies, or inadequate algorithm parameterization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the learning algorithm parameters (e.g., learning rate and discount factor). 2) Execute the algorithm and record the reward at each time step. 3) Identify the point at which the reward becomes stable or reaches the target value. 4) Count the number of time steps required to reach this point. 5) Compare results across different algorithm configurations.
References	1) PRS-P2P: A Prosumer Recommender System for Secure P2P Energy Trading using Q-Learning Towards 6G

Tabela 143: Metrics Catalog: Total Cost

Metric	Total Cost
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Total economic value required to execute a complete operation on a blockchain, considering all involved costs such as transactions, smart contract execution, and data storage.
Objective	To evaluate the overall economic efficiency of blockchain solutions, enabling comparison of implementations, functions, and optimization strategies such as off-chain storage to reduce costs.
Equation	$\text{Total Cost} = \text{Transaction Cost} + \text{Execution Cost} + \text{Storage Cost}.$
Comment	Lower total costs indicate more economically efficient solutions. More complex operations or large data storage tend to increase total cost. Strategies such as off-chain storage can significantly reduce this cost without compromising security.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy the smart contract on a testnet or production network. 2) Execute the main system functions. 3) Record transaction, execution, and storage costs separately. 4) Sum the costs to obtain the total cost per operation. 5) Compare scenarios with and without off-chain solutions.
References	1) Blockchain-Based Secure Voting Mechanism Underlying 5G Network

Tabela 144: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Capacity

Metric	Transaction Capacity
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Total amount of value available across all active payment channels in the Lightning Network, representing how much the network can transfer through off-chain transactions without directly using the main blockchain.
Objective	To evaluate the scalability potential and liquidity of the Lightning Network, indicating the level of adoption and the system's ability to support micropayments and instant transactions.
Equation	Total Capacity = sum of the capacities of all active payment channels in the Lightning Network.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater liquidity and higher ability to perform simultaneous transactions. Lower values may signal low adoption, limited channel opening, or liquidity concentration in a few nodes, which can affect decentralization.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify active nodes and channels in the Lightning Network using explorers or compatible clients. 2) Collect the declared capacity of each active channel. 3) Sum all channel capacities to obtain the network's total capacity. 4) Convert the value to other currencies if needed. 5) Track capacity evolution over time and relate it to network adoption events.
References	1) Where is the Light(ning) in the Taproot Dawn? Unveiling the Bitcoin Lightning (IP) Network

Tabela 145: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Confirmation Time

Metric	Transaction Confirmation Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Total time required for a transaction to be accepted, validated by consensus, and permanently recorded on the blockchain, from submission to final confirmation.
Objective	To evaluate the temporal efficiency of the consensus process in blockchain networks, enabling comparison of protocols and configurations in terms of transaction confirmation speed.
Equation	$T_{\text{confirm}} = \text{confirmation time} - \text{transaction submission time}$.
Comment	Shorter times indicate a faster and more responsive network. Higher values may reveal consensus bottlenecks, excessive validator communication, or network congestion, negatively affecting time-sensitive applications.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure the blockchain network and the target consensus protocol. 2) Submit transactions to the network in a controlled manner. 3) Record the submission and confirmation timestamps for each transaction. 4) Compute the confirmation time for each transaction. 5) Compare results across different protocols, network loads, or numbers of validators.
References	1) An Efficient Byzantine Consensus Mechanism Based on Healthcare Sector in Blockchain

Tabela 146: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Conflict Rate

Metric	Transaction Conflict Rate
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Proportion of transactions within a block that conflict with each other, meaning they cannot be executed simultaneously because they access or modify the same blockchain data or state.
Objective	To assess the potential for parallel transaction execution in a blockchain, identifying the degree of dependency among transactions and its impact on system performance.
Equation	Conflict Rate = (number of conflicting transactions/total number of transactions) * 100%.
Comment	Lower rates indicate greater opportunities for parallel execution, resulting in better performance. Higher rates reveal strong transaction dependencies, reducing parallelism gains and increasing the need for sequential execution.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) For each block, identify transactions that access or modify the same data. 2) Mark transactions that share dependencies as conflicting. 3) Count the number of conflicting transactions and the total number of transactions in the block. 4) Compute the conflict rate using the defined formula. 5) Repeat the analysis across different blocks or time periods to obtain statistics.
References	1) On Exploiting Transaction Concurrency to Speed Up Blockchains

Tabela 147: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Coverage

Metric	Transaction Coverage
Characteristic	Functional Suitability
Subcharacteristic	Functional Completeness
Definition	Proportion of transactions that are effectively observed by network monitoring nodes relative to the total number of transactions that are eventually included in valid blockchain blocks.
Objective	To assess how complete and reliable public blockchain monitoring is, indicating whether observers can capture most of the transactions that actually compose the ledger.
Equation	Coverage = (number of observed transactions/total number of transactions) * 100%.
Comment	Values close to 100% indicate high transparency and good network visibility. Lower values suggest that some transactions were not observed, which can compromise security, performance, or behavioral analyses.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy observer nodes in different network regions or positions. 2) Record all transactions received by these nodes. 3) Identify transactions that were actually included in valid blocks. 4) Compare the two transaction sets. 5) Compute the coverage rate and analyze its variation over time.
References	1) Behind Block Explorers: Public Blockchain Measurement and Security Implication

Tabela 148: Metrics Catalog: Average Gas Used per Transaction

Metric	Average Gas Used per Transaction
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Average amount of gas consumed to execute a transaction on an EVM-based blockchain, reflecting the computational effort required to complete the operation.
Objective	To assess the computational efficiency of transactions, enabling cost estimation, identification of heavy operations, and comparison across smart contracts or implementation versions.
Equation	$\text{Average Gas per Transaction} = \frac{\sum \text{GasUsed}}{\text{total number of transactions}}$
Comment	Higher values indicate more complex transactions, typically associated with storage writes or multiple contract calls. When combined with gas price, these values directly impact the financial cost of a transaction.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Execute transactions or smart contract functions on a testnet or production network. 2) Obtain the <code>gasUsed</code> value from each transaction receipt. 3) Record gas usage values. 4) Compute the average and, if needed, percentiles of gas consumed. 5) Compare results across different contracts, functions, or versions.
References	1) Empirically Analyzing Ethereum's Gas Mechanism

Tabela 149: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Processing Rate

Metric	Transaction Processing Rate (TPS)
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Number of transactions that a blockchain can process per unit of time, usually expressed in transactions per second (TPS).
Objective	To assess the capacity and scalability of a blockchain when processing large transaction volumes, indicating whether the system is suitable for high-performance applications.
Equation	$\text{TPS} = \frac{\text{number of processed transactions}}{\text{total execution time}}$
Comment	Higher values indicate greater processing capacity and better scalability. Lower values suggest bottlenecks in consensus, transaction execution, or network communication among nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Configure a test environment with a defined transaction workload. 2) Submit transactions to the network over a controlled period. 3) Record the total number of processed transactions. 4) Measure the total execution time. 5) Compute TPS and repeat the test under different load levels.
References	1) Distributed Ledger for Spammers' Resume

Tabela 150: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Reordering

Metric	Transaction Reordering
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Situation in which transactions sent by the same sender are received or processed out of the expected order, typically defined by the nonce. When this occurs, newer transactions may be delayed until earlier ones are confirmed.
Objective	To assess how network propagation and mempool policies affect transaction ordering, influencing predictability and the confirmation time perceived by users.
Equation	Reordering Rate = (number of out-of-order transactions / total number of transactions) * 100%.
Comment	Low rates indicate good transaction ordering and propagation. High rates suggest network delays, restrictive mempool policies, or geographic distribution effects, resulting in longer confirmation times and reduced predictability for users.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collect transaction data received by nodes, including sender, nonce, and arrival time. 2) Order transactions from each sender by arrival time. 3) Check whether the nonce sequence follows the expected order. 4) Count how many transactions are out of order. 5) Compute the reordering rate and analyze its variation over time.
References	1) Impact of Geo-Distribution and Mining Pools on Blockchains: A Study of Ethereum

Tabela 151: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Time

Metric	Transaction Time
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Time Behavior
Definition	Time required for a transaction sent to the network to be validated by consensus and permanently recorded on the blockchain.
Objective	To evaluate how quickly the blockchain confirms transactions, indicating the efficiency of consensus and the network's ability to respond under different load levels.
Equation	$T_{tx} = \text{transaction confirmation time} - \text{transaction submission time}.$
Comment	Shorter times indicate higher efficiency and better user experience. Higher values may reveal communication bottlenecks, consensus overload, or network scalability limitations.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Submit a set of transactions to the blockchain. 2) Record the submission and confirmation timestamps for each transaction. 3) Compute the transaction time for each transaction. 4) Obtain statistics such as mean, median, and percentiles (p50, p95, p99). 5) Repeat the analysis under different network loads and configurations.
References	1) B4SDC: A Blockchain System for Security Data Collection in MANETs

Tabela 152: Metrics Catalog: Transaction Rate

Metric	Transaction Rate
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Capacity
Definition	Number of transactions processed or confirmed by the blockchain within a given time interval, indicating the intensity of transaction flow in the network.
Objective	To assess the operational capacity of the blockchain to handle different transaction volumes, observing its behavior under load variations without degrading performance.
Equation	Transaction Rate = $\frac{\text{number of processed transactions}}{\text{observed time interval}}$.
Comment	Higher values indicate greater processing capacity and better utilization of the network. Very low values may indicate congestion, consensus limitations, or communication bottlenecks among nodes.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Define the observation time interval. 2) Count the number of transactions processed or confirmed during that interval. 3) Compute the rate by dividing total transactions by the observed time. 4) Repeat the measurement under different load levels. 5) Compare results over time or across different network configurations.
References	1) Effect of Miner Incentive on the Confirmation Time of Bitcoin Transactions

Tabela 153: Metrics Catalog: Type Conversion Error Rate

Metric	Type Conversion Error Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of failures that occur when a value is converted to an incompatible or out-of-range type during the execution of transactions or smart contracts. These errors may interrupt execution and consume resources without producing a useful result.
Objective	To assess the robustness of smart contracts and data validation mechanisms, identifying typing problems that can cause execution failures, rework, and wasted resources.
Equation	Typecast Error Rate = $(N_{\text{typecast errors}}/N_{\text{typecast operations}}) \times 100\%$.
Comment	Low values indicate more robust code and proper input validation. High values suggest poorly formatted data, unsafe conversions, or failures introduced by external integrations, compromising transaction integrity and increasing unnecessary resource consumption.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monitor transaction and contract execution to identify type conversion failures. 2) Count the total number of type conversion operations performed in the analyzed period. 3) Count how many of these operations resulted in errors. 4) Compute the type conversion error rate using the defined equation. 5) Analyze the results to identify patterns related to data sources or contract versions.
References	1) An Efficient Distributed and Secure Algorithm for Transaction Confirmation in IOTA Using Cloud Computing

Tabela 154: Metrics Catalog: Unknown Call Rate

Metric	Unknown Call Rate
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Proportion of calls or transactions sent by network nodes that fail to reach a valid or recognized destination. These calls fail because the destination node is unknown, nonexistent, or out of sync.
Objective	To evaluate the security and reliability of communication among nodes in distributed networks, identifying routing failures, synchronization problems, or anomalous behaviors that may compromise network integrity.
Equation	$U_{rate} = N_{unknown}/N_{total}$.
Comment	Low values indicate good connectivity and efficient communication among network nodes. High values suggest synchronization problems, routing failures, or the presence of invalid or malicious nodes, increasing computational waste and the risk of instability.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Monitor calls or transactions generated by each node over a defined period. 2) Identify calls that failed due to unknown or nonexistent destinations. 3) Count the total number of calls in the same period. 4) Compute the unknown call rate using the defined equation. 5) Analyze the rate over time to detect systemic failures or anomalous patterns.
References	1) An Efficient Distributed and Secure Algorithm for Transaction Confirmation in IOTA Using Cloud Computing

Tabela 155: Metrics Catalog: Gas–Time Ratio Variability

Metric	Gas–Time Ratio Variability
Characteristic	Performance Efficiency
Subcharacteristic	Resource Utilization
Definition	Statistical variation of the ratio between the gas consumed by a transaction and the real time required for its execution. This metric indicates how consistently gas cost reflects the actual computational effort.
Objective	To assess the consistency and predictability of the gas pricing model, identifying discrepancies between the gas cost and the real execution time of transactions.
Equation	$CoV = \sigma/\mu$, where σ is the standard deviation of the observed Time/Gas ratio and μ is the mean of that ratio.
Comment	Low values indicate that gas cost closely follows real execution time. High values reveal inconsistencies, suggesting that transactions with similar gas costs may require very different processing times.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Instrument the Ethereum client to measure the real execution time of transactions. 2) Collect execution time and gas consumption data for a set of transactions or opcodes. 3) Compute the Time/Gas ratio for each execution. 4) Compute the mean and standard deviation of these ratios. 5) Compute the coefficient of variation (CoV) and compare across different environments or operation types.
References	1) Empirically Analyzing Ethereum’s Gas Mechanism

Tabela 156: Metrics Catalog: Vulnerable Scarcity Index

Metric	Vulnerable Scarcity Index
Characteristic	Reliability
Subcharacteristic	Fault Tolerance
Definition	Indicator that measures the degree of concentration of providers responsible for essential services in a blockchain ecosystem, such as RPCs, wallets, APIs, SDKs, oracles, or similar infrastructure. A high index indicates dependence on few providers and a higher risk of systemic failures.
Objective	To assess the vulnerability of the blockchain ecosystem arising from dependence on infrastructure controlled by a small number of providers, estimating risks to availability, service continuity, and network resilience.
Equation	$VSI = 1 - (N_{\text{independent providers}}/N_{\text{total providers}})$, where values closer to 1 indicate greater vulnerable scarcity.
Comment	A high index reveals hidden structural centralization, where failures, attacks, or censorship of a few providers can compromise a large portion of the ecosystem. Low values indicate greater provider diversity and higher fault tolerance.
Scale Type	Ratio
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify the critical services used by the blockchain ecosystem. 2) Map the providers responsible for each service. 3) Identify which providers are independent from each other. 4) Compute the VSI based on the proportion of independent providers. 5) Analyze the result to identify centralization risks and single points of failure.
References	1) Bad Apples: Understanding the Centralized Security Risks in Decentralized Ecosystems

Tabela 157: Metrics Catalog: Winning Bid Validation

Metric	Winning Bid Validation
Characteristic	Security
Subcharacteristic	Integrity
Definition	Ability of a blockchain-based system to correctly confirm which bid is the highest in an electronic auction, without revealing the values of losing bids. Validation is performed in a decentralized and cryptographically verifiable manner.
Objective	To ensure the integrity and trustworthiness of on-chain auction results, allowing any participant to verify the winning price without relying on a central auditor and without compromising bid privacy.
Equation	Validation is performed through cryptographic comparison of bid commitments, verifying that the winning bid is greater than the others without revealing individual values.
Comment	Correct validation ensures that the auction was fair and that the highest bid actually won. Failures in this process undermine trust in the system and may indicate flaws in the cryptographic implementation or the smart contract.
Scale Type	Nominal
Protocol	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Each participant submits their bid as a cryptographic commitment on the blockchain. 2) The smart contract identifies the commitment corresponding to the highest bid. 3) Cryptographic proofs are generated showing that the winning bid is greater than the others without revealing values. 4) Participants or observers verify the published proofs. 5) The contract confirms the winner and finalizes the auction.
References	1) A Blockchain-Based Sealed-Bid e-Auction Scheme with Smart Contract and Zero-Knowledge Proof